

MAINSTREAM BIO

MAINSTREAMING SMALL-SCALE BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS ACROSS RURAL EUROPE

D5.3

Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities - final version

WHITE

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The methodology of MainstreamBIO (GA No 101059420) for the project's Dissemination and Communication Plan builds upon an existing know-how, tools and templates that were internally developed by White Research while also taking into account EC guidelines and good practices available in literature. Part of the adopted standard methodology has been developed and employed in previous research projects where White Research served as beneficiary, such as in the INCENTIVE (GA No. 101005330) and POP-Machina (GA No. 821479) projects. For the MainstreamBIO-employed methodology, ad hoc and tailored modifications were integrated in order to comply with the GA conditions, EU recommendations and project particularities. Along these lines, this deliverable presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied in the context of MainstreamBIO.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BG	Bulgaria
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
Coms.	Communication(s)
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
DCP	Dissemination & Communication Plan
DK	Denmark
ES	Spain
EuRCBC	European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference
GA	Grant Agreement
IE	Ireland
MIPs	Multi-actor Innovation Platforms
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NL	Netherlands
PL	Poland
R&I	Research and Innovation
RBA	Rural Bioeconomy Alliance
SE	Sweden
SHs	Stakeholders
SMA	Social Media Accounts
SME	Small-medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable **D5.3** presents the **final version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)** for the MainstreamBIO project. It builds upon the two previous versions submitted in M3 and M18, which laid the foundation for the project's communication and dissemination strategy and were progressively refined to align with the project's evolving objectives and progress. The initial plan (M3) set out the core principles, tools, and channels for outreach, while the M18 version incorporated updates and adjustments based on the lessons learned and the needs that emerged by the project's midpoint. This final version provides a comprehensive and detailed overview of all dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the duration of the project, both at local and European levels. It showcases the coordinated efforts of the consortium to reach relevant stakeholders across multiple sectors and regions, using targeted messaging and a variety of tailored tools and channels. Particular attention is paid to stakeholder engagement - highlighting how feedback from stakeholders has been actively used to inform and adapt the project's communication strategy and overall direction.

The document also reflects on the success and impact of these efforts in relation to the established KPIs and offers insights into the role of dissemination in supporting broader project objectives, including awareness-raising, knowledge transfer, and policy influence. Ultimately, this deliverable serves as both a record of achievements and a guide for sustaining communication and visibility beyond the project's formal completion. The present version has been updated taking into consideration experience gathered in the second half of the project, while also assessing the effectiveness of the activities that have been implemented since the very beginning of the project, namely September 2022. All lessons learnt have been used to adapt the D&C strategy of the project to provide an analysis of the dissemination activities through a specific monitoring process of the project's KPIs.

In particular, the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction to the final DCP and its purpose** | This chapter introduces the final version of MainstreamBIO's Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP), outlining its revised objectives and the strategy followed to ensure meaningful outreach, stakeholder engagement, and long-term visibility of project results.
- **Chapter 2: MainstreamBIO project overview** | A concise summary of the MainstreamBIO project, its mission, and the importance of promoting small-scale, bio-based solutions adapted to regional contexts.
- **Chapter 3: Dissemination and communication strategy & goals** | An updated look at the D&C strategy, highlighting how communication goals evolved throughout the project lifecycle. This section outlines the refined approach taken in the final year and lessons learned for improved stakeholder targeting and message delivery.
- **Chapter 4: Key target audiences and communication focus** | This chapter maps the project's main stakeholder groups (e.g. rural communities, SMEs, policymakers, researchers), explores tailored messaging, and presents strategies for engaging each audience effectively across different phases of the project.
- **Chapter 5-8: Communication tools and dissemination channels** | An overview of the main tools and platforms used to share MainstreamBIO's activities and results - including the project website, newsletters, social media, factsheets, videos, internal/external events and publications - along with insights on their effectiveness.

- **Chapter 9: Synergies and joint activities with external projects** | A presentation of collaborative activities conducted with sister and clustered projects to boost mutual visibility and co-dissemination. It also includes a summary of joint initiatives and how they contributed to MainstreamBIO's outreach KPIs.
- **Chapter 10: KPIs monitoring and progress reporting** | This section outlines the project's KPIs for dissemination and communication, the methods used to track progress, and a reflection on achievements and areas where targets were exceeded or under-delivered.
- **Chapter 11: Dissemination timeline and long-term vision** | An outline of the implementation timeline divided across the project's phases, identifying key milestones, and offering a forward-looking plan for post-project dissemination to ensure that MainstreamBIO's results continue to be visible and impactful beyond its official end.

Throughout the project, MainstreamBIO has implemented a diverse set of dissemination and communication activities, successfully engaging a wide range of stakeholders across Europe. The cumulative outreach of these actions exceeded 27,029 stakeholders. In parallel, the project's online presence, particularly via social media platforms & project's website, helped to connect with more than 8,000 individuals through regular updates, campaigns, and knowledge-sharing posts.

A review of the project's outreach impact indicates that the most effective tools for stakeholder engagement included: (i) contributions to relevant third-party events, both physical and digital; (ii) the implementation of project's workshops and awareness raising campaigns; and (iii) consistent visibility through digital communication, notably via the MainstreamBIO website and social media accounts. These efforts collectively contributed to building recognition for MainstreamBIO and its mission, ensuring a strong and well-targeted presence within the broader bioeconomy ecosystem.

1. Introduction

This report outlines the final strategy behind MainstreamBIO’s dissemination and communication (D&C) activities and presents the outcomes achieved by M36. It also describes the established operational framework through which project partners promoted the initiative, communicated its activities, and disseminated its results.

The Dissemination & Communication Plan (DCP) has been continuously evolving since the release of its initial version in M3. Building on both the original and updated versions, this final DCP provides a comprehensive overview of all planned and implemented activities designed to promote MainstreamBIO and deliver its key messages to a broad spectrum of stakeholders at local, national, and international levels. All actions and communication channels have been systematically monitored and internally assessed to measure their effectiveness and ensure that the strategy was continuously refined based on evidence and experience gained.

The main objective of the final version of the DCP has been to provide a clear overview of the channels, tools, actions, and methods deployed to maximise the project’s impact and extend its reach across different stakeholder groups. Since the beginning of the project, it has been essential to disseminate and effectively communicate the project’s vision and results to ensure the successful implementation of the MainstreamBIO Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy. The main objective of MainstreamBIO’s D&C Strategy, as presented in D5.1, was to define the actions to be carried out and the tools to be used for the communication and promotion of the project’s results. Indeed, the DCP served as a guiding framework for the consortium’s communication and dissemination activities throughout the project’s lifecycle.

This D&C strategy and plan define the following aspects in relation to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities:

Table 1. Key aspects of the D&C strategy of MainstreamBIO

Key Questions	MainstreamBIO’s DCP
What ?	Key messages
To whom ?	Target audiences
Who ?	Roles & Responsibilities
How ?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, and templates
When ?	Timeline

Accordingly, this document outlines the fundamental elements of an efficient refined dissemination strategy by:

- **Bringing multiple objectives** of communication and dissemination activities;
- **Defining** and **assigning** to the partners the **actions** and **obligations** required for the communication and dissemination process;
- Establishing **key target audiences**;
- Displaying the **primary information** of the project and laying out **the main assets**;

- **Enumerate the tools and communication channels**, which have been utilised to reach the target audience, as well as, the **requisite actions** and **resources**;
- Outlining the **internal monitoring, evaluation** and **reporting** of dissemination activities;
- Distributing an **indicative schedule of promotional activities** that occurred during the life cycle of the project;
- Delivering the **applicable guidelines** and **the corresponding templates** for the greatest promotion of the project's results.

Communication and dissemination activities were implemented throughout the entire lifespan of the project (M1-M36) under the dedicated Work Package (WP5 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation). Actions aimed both at raising awareness of the project's activities and as a feedback mechanism, leading to greater adjustments of the consortium's functions. Hence, the partners have been continuously guided to emphasise on communicating the messages and findings elicited from MainstreamBIO, while engaging stakeholders across a wide selection of both online and physical tools and channels.

It should be underlined that a well-developed and effective dissemination strategy requires the active involvement of all partners, who devote time and resources with the intention of spreading awareness about the project and successfully interacting with the intended audience.

Additionally, it is important to emphasise that both the dissemination guidelines and the monitoring templates (Annex 1: MainstreamBIO initial dissemination and communication guidelines for consortium partners) have been updated in accordance with the project's development and the knowledge gained via the project's numerous activities.

The monitoring and assessment of communication activities throughout the project's three-year duration (M1–M36) have informed key refinements in this final version of the Dissemination & Communication Plan. These adjustments were strategically implemented to enhance the effectiveness of outreach efforts and ensure the successful achievement of all dissemination KPIs. Particular emphasis was placed on strengthening engagement where progress had been slower, such as increasing unique visits to the MainstreamBIO website and supporting collaborative activities with clustered projects. Additionally, recognising the importance of expanding the project's reach, targeted efforts were made to proactively participate in external events, facilitating connections with key stakeholders and maximising the project's overall impact. This final DCP reflects the extensive efforts undertaken to disseminate MainstreamBIO's activities and results effectively, ensuring their visibility and long-term value for bioeconomy sector.

2. About MainstreamBIO

The potential of **bio-based products and solutions in driving a sustainable economy** has been increasingly acknowledged through the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. The development of the bioeconomy holds significant promise for fostering sustainable growth in the EU, contributing to key policy goals. As a central component of the EU's economic transformation, **bio-based solutions offer opportunities for green job creation and play a vital role** in addressing industrial, environmental, and societal challenges. Despite substantial investments, several European regions had not yet fully capitalised on this potential at the onset of the project. **MainstreamBIO responded to this need** by enabling broader engagement of rural actors in the bioeconomy landscape.

Throughout its implementation, MainstreamBIO has successfully brought **small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe**. Through the establishment of MIPs in seven EU regions, in Poland; Denmark; Sweden; Bulgaria; Spain; Ireland, and the Netherlands, and the deployment of **targeted support services** the project has provided rural stakeholders with meaningful opportunities to engage in and accelerate the development of the bioeconomy. These MIPs served as regional hubs that connected actors with diverse backgrounds, fostering collaboration and partnership-building across the value chain.

A major achievement of the project was the delivery of **comprehensive innovation support services, covering both technical and business aspects**. On the technical side, MainstreamBIO offered guidance on the deployment and optimization of small-scale bio-based solutions, assistance with data collection (e.g., bio-mass balance, energy use), support in pilot design and execution, recommendations for nutrient recycling practices, and monitoring strategies.

Complementing these services, **MainstreamBIO developed and launched an interactive Digital Toolkit**, a central element of its support strategy. This toolkit consolidated key resources to scale up bio-based initiatives, including a catalogue of small-scale technologies, business models and social innovations, a best practice guide for nutrient recycling, a Bio Forum, a Decision Support System, a repository of bioeconomy knowledge, and a tools library. By offering these resources openly, the project has significantly contributed to the growth of regional bioeconomy ecosystems and has laid a strong foundation for continued innovation and stakeholder engagement beyond its duration.

By carrying out the previously mentioned actions, MainstreamBIO achieved the following goals:

- ✓ **Goal 1:** Established regional Multi-actor Innovation Platforms that brought together and enhanced cooperation between key stakeholders, opening up sustainable bio-based business model paths in rural areas.
- ✓ **Goal 2:** Co-developed innovation support services and digital tools that built awareness, understanding and capacity to uptake small-scale bio-based solutions in line with market demand and regional specificities.
- ✓ **Goal 3:** Delivered tailored innovation support services to accelerate the deployment of scientific and practical knowledge, introducing bio-based solutions to the market along with marketable products and services.
- ✓ **Goal 4:** Evaluated results and used evidence to drive multi-actor dialogues, peer learning and knowledge transfer, delivering guidelines and recommendations for replication in rural areas across Europe.
- ✓ **Goal 5:** Raised awareness, clustered with relevant initiatives and communicated the project, disseminating its results, while also acting towards their widespread adoption and sustainable exploitation.

3. Dissemination and Communication Plan

The MainstreamBIO Dissemination & Communication Plan (DCP) was developed to establish a clear strategy for dissemination activities and facilitate project’s objectives and goals. This is a horizontal action, meaning that the DCP is connected to all parts of the workplan and its respective activities.

3.1 Overview

The MainstreamBIO Dissemination & Communication (D&C) strategy for stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination activities was developed in alignment with the project’s overall concept and approach to support the achievement of its objectives. The primary aim of the strategy was to ensure wide-reaching visibility and maximise the impact of the project’s results - by leveraging the existing knowledge within the consortium, transferring insights gained during the project to relevant stakeholders, and effectively communicating outcomes to broader audiences. The strategy also set out clear guidelines for the implementation of all dissemination activities, covering both strategic direction and operational elements throughout the project lifecycle. These elements are illustrated in the figure below¹:

Figure 1. Overview of the MainstreamBIO D&C strategy

To ensure successful outcomes, the communication and dissemination strategy was translated into a practical and realistic plan from the beginning, paying close attention to defining the details of the

¹ Inspired by Fig.1 of: Gaillard, M., and N. Germain, “Deliverable 9.2 – Dissemination and communication plan”, DTOceanPlus, France Energies Marines, 10 December 2018, p.10.

elements shown above at a very early stage, including the appropriate tools, channels and actions to engage the target audiences. All key elements for successful communication and dissemination were frequently reviewed, including: **what should be** communicated (project concepts, outcomes and assets) and **why**, to **whom** (target groups), by **what means** (tools, channels, etc.) and **when**.

3.2 Objectives

MainstreamBIO’s communication and dissemination efforts aimed to raise awareness of the project and ensure high visibility of its events and activities. These efforts were instrumental in promoting the project’s vision, implementation progress, and results to a wide range of stakeholders. In doing so, the DCP supported various work packages and contributed to the exploitation of MainstreamBIO’s outputs, reinforcing the project’s overall impact through the effective use of generated knowledge.

To support the smooth execution and effective oversight of all dissemination and communication efforts, MainstreamBIO defined a series of clear and attainable objectives. These goals helped clarify the rationale behind establishing a comprehensive dissemination strategy and are briefly outlined below, as initially introduced in D5.1:

- **Promote** MainstreamBIO’s activities and innovative bio-based solutions.
- **Raise** awareness of the bioeconomy, bio-based products, and nutrient circularity.
- **Encourage** involvement in project’s activities
- **Boost** participation in conferences and events to enhance visibility and networking.
- **Ensure** key messages effectively reach and engage target audiences.
- **Disseminate** key outcomes such as MIPs, digital toolkit, partnerships, and services.
- **Define** partner roles and responsibilities for a coordinated dissemination approach.
- **Strengthen** partner involvement to amplify communication and outreach.
- **Expand** result dissemination through partner networks for lasting impact.
- **Support** collaboration with related initiatives to build synergies and reach.

Following MainstreamBIO’s official completion, it is evident that the core dissemination and communication objectives set at the outset have been effectively fulfilled. The table below outlines how these goals were met through well-coordinated activities, consistent partner involvement, and a proactive approach to stakeholder engagement. Strategic efforts in visibility, outreach, and result promotion ensured that project outcomes reached a broad and relevant audience. Each objective was met through carefully planned actions, contributing to the wider uptake of project insights and services. The practices developed and refined throughout the project will serve as a valuable reference for future initiatives aiming to support the bioeconomy in rural regions.

Table 2. D&C Objectives and Implementation approach

D&C Objectives	Implementation Approach
Promote Project’s activities and innovative bio-based solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Launched and maintained a project website as a central information source. ✓ Produced brochures, newsletters, and videos to present key goals and results. ✓ Developed and managed SMAs (LinkedIn; Facebook; X; YouTube) to engage a wider audience.
Raise awareness of the bio-sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Held numerous events (campaigns, webinars, workshops) to promote project’s insights.

D&C Objectives	Implementation Approach
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Shared deliverables, articles, and briefs online to inform key audiences. ✓ Maintained stakeholder contact via newsletters and direct outreach.
Encourage involvement in MainstreamBIO's activities	✓ Ran targeted dissemination campaigns for each activity (e.g., Open Call, webinars, workshops) before and after implementation.
Boost participation in conferences and events	✓ Kept track of notable EU bioeconomy events and informed partners to explore MainstreamBIO's potential participation.
Ensure key messages effectively reach target audiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Designed a targeted communication approach with specific messages for each stakeholder group. ✓ Maintained consistent and clear messaging across all platforms. ✓ Applied visual content to improve message delivery and understanding.
Disseminate MainstreamBIO's key outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Established a structured plan for publishing articles and social media posts across all project channels. ✓ Leveraged additional tools like the newsletter, scientific publications, and promotional video to enhance outreach.
Define partner roles; involvement and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Developed and circulated tailored D&C guidelines and monitoring templates for the consortium ✓ Enabled efficient tracking of all dissemination and communication activities across the consortium.
Expand result dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Shared project findings, lessons learned, and outcomes with wider audiences. ✓ Published open-access scientific articles and implemented awareness campaigns to promote knowledge exchange.
Support collaboration with related projects and initiatives	✓ Collaborated with EU-funded projects on related topics, highlighted by the establishment of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance.

3.3 Roles and responsibilities

All the members of the consortium played a key role in MainstreamBIO's communication activities, in order to fulfil the goals and objectives set by the initial DCP plan (D5.1). The participation and contribution of partners had a direct impact on the project's development, such as the activities, results, and overall progress, which were promoted through dissemination activities and communication tools.

Therefore, partners were expected to assist and support the project's online presence, both by providing appropriate material for project's social media and website, but also promoting the posts in order to gain more followers who will stay informed about MainstreamBIO's actions and results. Furthermore, partners were continuously encouraged to support the project's wider promotion by attending relevant events/conferences and publishing in online and offline publications (e.g. websites, newspapers, magazines etc.).

At the end of each project semester, all partners filled out the Dissemination Reporting template to present the main dissemination actions they carried out during the semester (an example of the completed template provided in [Annex 2: Dissemination Reporting Template](#)). In addition to the Dissemination Reporting template, partners were asked to complete the Event's Reporting templates ([Annex 3: Internal Events Reporting Template](#) & [Annex 4: External Events Reporting Template](#)) for each event they either organised or participated in, during the semester, presenting the main dissemination actions that occurred in that specific event.

Taking the above into account and evaluating the progress of D&C activities and the achievement of the related KPIs, it is evident that the consortium partners provided strong support in the following areas:

Online dissemination efforts:

- Contributed content ideas for the project website, social media platforms, and newsletters (e.g. LinkedIn/Facebook posts, articles on bioeconomy; interviews or project updates).
- Promoted MainstreamBIO's website; newsletter and social media channels within their own networks.
- Informed the dissemination team about bioeconomy-related news or events that could inspire content creation.

Offline dissemination actions:

- Organised and supported events to increase visibility and awareness of MainstreamBIO at the regional and EU levels.
- Shared project materials such as leaflets; banners and posters during workshops and meetings.
- Ensured broad dissemination of MainstreamBIO by attending and contributing to external events; conferences and through publications in various media (print and online).

4. Target audiences and tailored messages

4.1 The MainstreamBIO target audiences

The primary goal of dissemination and communication activities was to disseminate information about the project's vision, what results from it, and which problems were solved, thereby maximising the project's impact. As a result, it was critical to define the target groups to whom the DCP plan is directed.

The experience and lessons learned throughout the implementation of the project led to identifying new target groups not initially identified, which are international organisations and standardisation and certification bodies. Figure 2 below presents the updated target audiences of MainstreamBIO.

Figure 2. MainstreamBIO's target audiences

MainstreamBIO used the Stakeholders Classification Model¹ to ensure that the list of targeted audiences is comprehensive, simple, and easy-to-understand. This model categorises each stakeholder group based on specific parameters such as:

- The level of authority of each stakeholder;

¹ Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Helena Alves, Mário Raposo, (2012). "A model for stakeholder classification and stakeholder relationships", Management Decision, Vol. 50 Issue: 10, pp. 1861-1879.

- The stakeholder's interest in the project's outcomes;
- The extent of the stakeholder's active participation in the project;
- The stakeholder's influence over the project's design, potential changes or modifications, and outcomes.

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement

The parameters mentioned above define changes in communication tools and messages. Figure 3 summarises these parameters and how the various types of stakeholder engagement are classified.

Following that, Table 3 presents a brief description of each target group/subgroup, along with the engagement measures that MainstreamBIO's D&C activities followed:

Table 3. Target groups/sub-groups and engagement measures

Target Groups	Sub-groups	Engagement Measures
Bio-mass producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers; • Forestry; • Aquaculture; • Unions; • Associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scale-up workshops ✓ Mutual Learning workshops ✓ Website articles/publications ✓ Social media campaigns ✓ Awareness raising campaigns ✓ Networking events
Bio-industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobased & agri-food industry; • Industrial operators and traders; • SMEs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scale-up workshops ✓ Mutual Learning workshops ✓ Website articles/publications ✓ Social media campaigns ✓ Awareness raising campaigns ✓ Webinars ✓ Networking events

Target Groups	Sub-groups	Engagement Measures
Innovation intermediaries in agriculture & bioeconomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developer; • Business model innovators; • Intellectual property managers; • Services innovators; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scale-up workshops ✓ Webinars ✓ Policy roundtables ✓ Website articles/publications
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU/national/regional authorities; • Development agencies; • Innovation and policy advisors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scale-up workshops ✓ Webinars ✓ Policy roundtables ✓ Website articles/publications ✓ Social media campaigns
Researchers & academia, including R&I projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public/private research institutes; • Universities; • Researchers; • Educators; • Administrators; • Students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientific publications ✓ Mutual Learning workshops ✓ Website articles/publications ✓ Social media campaigns ✓ Awareness raising campaigns
Civil society, consumers & action groups included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSOs • NGOs • Environmental organisations • General Public • Civil Society organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientific publications ✓ Mutual Learning workshops ✓ Website articles/publications ✓ Social media campaigns ✓ Awareness raising campaigns ✓ Networking events
Financial institutions & individual investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private equity firms • Venture capital • Commercial/promotional banks funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scale-up workshops ✓ Mutual Learning workshops ✓ Website articles/publications ✓ Social media campaigns ✓ Awareness raising campaigns ✓ Webinars
Standardisation and Certification Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bodies establishing standards and certifications for bio-based products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Awareness raising campaigns ✓ Webinars ✓ Networking events ✓ Scientific Publications
International organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisations and Specialised agencies promoting global cooperation in the bioeconomy development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Networking events ✓ Scientific Publications

4.2 The MainstreamBIO key messages

The main messages communicated to the target groups are an important aspect of an effective dissemination and communication plan. These messages must be aligned with project's concept and vision, but they must also be tailored to the needs of the target audiences.

This is also the main reason why different stakeholder groups have been addressed through different messages. For the same reason, the messages that have been delivered during MainstreamBIO were subject to changes and were constantly optimised based on the experience gained and the monitoring of the dissemination results.

The target audiences; the key messages and the MainstreamBIO's assets that communicate the different key messages to the various target groups are listed in Table 4 below:

Table 4. MainstreamBIO's target groups; needs; key messages and related assets

Target group	Needs	Key Messages	MainstreamBIO's related assets
<p><i>Farmers and business (agri-food & bio-based industry, logistics, financing)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increased economic activities; ○ Having actual data about market trends and innovative biobased solutions; ○ Comply with the evolving regulatory framework; ○ Enhanced cooperation with major key actors of the value chain; ○ Access to finance and support services; ○ Communicate sector's needs and challenges; ○ Information about consumers needs and preferences in relation to biobased products; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Information about entrepreneurial and career opportunities within bioeconomy ; ● Market insights that can help biobased industry to increase biobased products & services marketability; ● Access to evidence-based data about successful biobased projects; ● Technical and innovation support services shaped to regional needs and contexts; ● Identification of the biobased solutions that best match the respective market conditions and increase their uptake; ● A multi-actor approach that stimulates innovation in bioeconomy development and establishes pathways between bioeconomy development policies and funding sources at both regional, national and international level; ● A collaborative bioeconomy network that engages and consults key regional bioeconomy actors, while enabling dialogue amongst key rural actors; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Multi-actor Innovation Platforms; ➔ Open Call & Innovation supporting services; ➔ Digital Toolkit; ➔ Workshops and webinars ➔ Awareness raising campaigns ➔ Networking events

Target group	Needs	Key Messages	MainstreamBIO's related assets
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A network of synergies with other relevant EU projects supporting the bioeconomy development in rural areas; • Data about consumers' needs and preferences in relation to biobased products to develop market-driven biobased products and services; 	
<p><i>Intermediaries; advisors & policy makers</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Improve their support practices; ○ Consult clients efficiently; ○ Create a strong client base; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about new markets and opportunities arising to enhance support practices and advice; • Data in relation to current regional challenges of rural actors to effectively engage and mobilise them; • A business-support network connecting various value chain actors, including operators, customers, technology providers, and advisors; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Digital Toolkit; ➔ Workshops and webinars ➔ WP1 & WP2 research results ➔ Networking events
<p><i>Government/Policy-makers/Public authorities</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Understanding the current needs and challenges of the bioeconomy value chains; ○ An effective policy framework that will assist in meeting national and regional policy targets; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and figures on regional needs, concerns, barriers and challenges of the key actors involved in bioeconomy development in the targeted rural areas; • Policy recommendations to improve existing policy frameworks for mainstreaming bio-based solutions across rural Europe; • Evidence-based support measures that can be used as policy options to accelerate the adoption of small-scale biobased solutions; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Digital Toolkit; ➔ Workshops and webinars ➔ WP1 & WP2 research results ➔ Networking events ➔ Policy roundtables

Target group	Needs	Key Messages	MainstreamBIO's related assets
<i>Researchers and academia</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enhance research in focal scientific disciplines; ○ Information about the evolving industry trends; ○ Establishing new collaborations; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research findings about regional trends of biobased industries in the targeted rural areas; ● A suite of educational resources and tools for tapping into scientific knowledge about bio-based industries in rural areas; ● Support to access networks allowing to build strong collaborations and synergies; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Digital Toolkit; ➔ Workshops and webinars ➔ WP1 & WP2 research results ➔ Scientific Publications ➔ Networking events ➔ Policy roundtables
<i>Civil society and action groups</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Safe, healthy and affordable food; ○ Stronger job market; ○ Information about the benefits of biobased products and solutions; ○ Incentives to support biobased market and adopt a sustainable living; ○ Communicate concerns about biobased products & solutions; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The socio-economic and environmental benefits of bioeconomy development and biobased products; ● Information about health benefits of replacing fossil-based products with biobased products; ● Enhance awareness in relation to bioeconomy's positive impact on regional economic activities and the creation of green jobs; ● A bioeconomy network connecting various actors of the value chain, allowing to share their concerns and experiences; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Workshops and webinars; ➔ Awareness raising campaigns; ➔ WP1 & WP2 research results ➔ Scientific Publications ➔ Networking events

Target group	Needs	Key Messages	MainstreamBIO's related assets
<p><i>Standardisation and Certification Bodies</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enhance adoption of certification labels in the bioeconomy sector; ○ Increase credibility of certification schemes; ○ Updating certification standards regularly; ○ Exchange best practices on the improvement of the certification processes; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The potential weakness of labels in the market; ● Means to increase the adoption of effective labels; ● How to enhance the performance of their schemes through best practices; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Workshops and webinars; ➔ Awareness raising campaigns ➔ WP1 & WP2 research results ➔ Scientific Publications ➔ Networking events ➔ Policy roundtables
<p><i>International Organisations</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Receiving information on the development of biobased products and solutions worldwide; ○ Obtaining access to data regarding benefits of biobased products and solutions; ○ Best practices exchange; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Environmental, economic and social advantages to the development of bioeconomy; ● Raising awareness on the positive impact related to biobased products and solutions and its impact on local communities; ● Establishing a global bioeconomy network linking different actors to share experiences and lessons learned in the field of bioeconomy; 	

5. Dissemination and Communication tools and channels

5.1 Dissemination channels and activities

The D&C Strategy of MainstreamBIO deployed a wide range of tools and channels ensuring project's full visibility and promotion to a range of stakeholders. The channels and tools used refer to physical and online presence related to the goals set by MainstreamBIO's D&C strategy. Figure 4 depicts a dissemination and communication flow chart for MainstreamBIO ongoing activities:

Figure 4. MainstreamBIO's communication activities, channels and tools

MainstreamBIO's promotional material and graphical identity

- Logo and project visual and written identity
- [Leaflet](#)
- [Poster](#)
- Banner
- Templates (i.e. for publications, and presentations)
- MainstreamBIO [promotional video](#)
- Other ad-hoc promotional material (i.e. press releases, infographics)

MainstreamBIO's online presence

- MainstreamBIO's [website](#)
- MAINSTREAMBIO's [Digital Toolkit](#)
- Bi-annual [Newsletter](#)

MainstreamBIO's Social Media Accounts (SMAs)

- [X \(former Twitter\)](#)
- [Facebook](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [YouTube](#)

Events

- MainstreamBIO's capacity building workshops
- MainstreamBIO's co-creation workshops

- MainstreamBIO’s networking & demo days
- MainstreamBIO’s awareness raising and educational events
- MainstreamBIO’s mutual learning workshops
- MainstreamBIO’s scale-up workshops
- MainstreamBIO’s policy roundtable
- Final dissemination event
- Participating in external events to keep in touch with stakeholders, exchange knowledge and promote project.

Publications

- MainstreamBIO’s public deliverables
- Other publications (e.g. scientific publications ; posters ; magazines, newsletters, online media, etc.)

Synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives and dialogue with association members

- Complementary projects e.g. sister projects funded by CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-02 or other related projects
- Regional/national/international initiatives

The expected use of communication and dissemination channels by the consortium is described in the dedicated guidelines (Annex 1). A more detailed description of each channel is provided in section 4.

Table 5. Overview of the tools to be used to reach different target audiences

Target Group - Coms. tools	Tools and Channels								
	Farmers, farmer groups/ associations	Biobased & agri-food industry/SMEs	Innovation intermediaries	Innovation and policy advisors	Policy makers	Researchers, academia	Financial institutions /individual investors	International Organisations	Standardisation & certification bodies
Promotional material	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Social media	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Digital media (website; digital toolkit; newsletter)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

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Capacity building workshops	x	x	x						
Networking & demo days	x	x	x			x	x	x	x
Awareness raising & educational events	x	x							
Mutual learning workshops	x	x							
Final dissemination event	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Policy roundtable				x	x	x	x		
External Events	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Publications	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

5.2 Promotional material

The promotional material of MainstreamBIO was developed during the early stages of the project, with WHITE leading the content development and graphic design. Consortium partners shared their feedback during the development process to ensure alignment with the project's objectives and visual identity. All materials - both printable and digital - have been made [freely accessible](#) to the public via the project's website and have also been uploaded to the shared consortium repository, allowing partners to download, print, and use them as needed. The promotional materials were used across various internal and external events to raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and communicate the project's mission and objectives. The design and messaging of all materials reflect the unique identity of MainstreamBIO, as outlined in the following section.

5.2.1 Logo

The [project logo](#), in conjunction with the general graphic elements and the aesthetic concept, is what distinguishes the project and served as the foundation for the further development of the entire promotion package (e.g. leaflets; posters; infographics; newsletters; deliverables; social media; web-portal; publications; publicity for internal and external events, etc.) that was used in all dissemination and communications activities.

Since the very beginning of MainstreamBIO (M1), the project partners were invited to participate in an online voting for the project's logo, where a variety of logo options were presented to them. Figure 5 illustrates the logo which received the majority of the votes.

Figure 5. MainstreamBIO's logo

The logo icon is a combination of 3 elements starting from the left with three curved lines that symbolises a rural area and at the same time creates the letter *M* in an abstract way with the combination of the leaf icon on the right. The cog on the top is the connection between the rural *M* and the leaf and constitutes the mean for bio-based transformation and production.

The color palette (Figure 6) combines shades of greens which are representative colors for bio-based production, bioeconomy and sustainability.

Figure 6. MainstreamBIO's color palette

In addition to the MainstreamBIO logo, in any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc. produced in the frame of the project, the EU flag and funding statement has been shown:

Figure 7. EU emblem and disclaimer

5.2.2 Leaflet; poster and additional promotional materials

Throughout the project's implementation, the **leaflet** and **poster** ([Annex 5: MainstreamBIO's Leaflet; Poster & Banner](#)) proved to be valuable tools in supporting MainstreamBIO's dissemination and communication efforts. Developed in M3, both materials were carefully designed to reflect the project's visual identity and effectively communicate its core messages. The leaflet provided a concise yet comprehensive overview of MainstreamBIO's concept, objectives, expected outcomes, and contact information, while the poster visually illustrated the project's goals and methodology in an engaging and accessible way.

These promotional tools also included key details about the consortium, project website, social media accounts, and Horizon Europe funding acknowledgment, ensuring consistent and informative outreach across all stakeholder groups. Made publicly available on the project's website for download, their accessibility and professional presentation significantly contributed to increasing visibility.

Promotional materials such as the leaflet and poster played a central role in conveying MainstreamBIO's visual identity and key messages throughout the project's lifecycle. These materials served as effective tools to increase project visibility, offering a quick yet informative overview of MainstreamBIO's objectives, key partners, communication channels, and branding elements. The poster was particularly useful in conferences and during public presentations, while the leaflet proved instrumental in raising awareness at both internal and external events by providing accessible and engaging content for stakeholders.

By the end of the project, **773 leaflets and posters had been downloaded** from the project website. In addition, a total of **547 printed promotional material** was distributed across various internal and external events. These numbers highlight the significant interest generated around MainstreamBIO and confirm the important role of well-designed promotional tools in enhancing communication outreach and stakeholder engagement.

Additional promotional material

To enhance its dissemination and communication outreach, MainstreamBIO produced additional promotional material (e.g., banner and QR code), when considered necessary to maximise the project's visibility.

The MainstreamBIO **banner** ([Annex 5: MainstreamBIO's Leaflet; Poster & Banner](#)) was designed with the intent to increase the project's visibility when attending at internal and external events, for this reason, it contains all relevant information on the project from consortium partners, to project's aims and approaches, social media accounts and contact information.

Furthermore, a MainstreamBIO website **QR code** was created as an additional easy-to-use communication tool to promote the project. When attending internal and external events, it proved to be a very useful and efficient tool to promote MainstreamBIO among a wide range of bioeconomy stakeholders while also being more environmentally friendly.

Figure 8. MainstreamBIO website QR code

5.2.3 Templates

Ensuring consistency and coherence across all dissemination activities was a key objective of MainstreamBIO’s Dissemination and Communication Plan. To support this, a set of **dedicated templates** was developed early in the project (M2), incorporating visual elements aligned with the project’s graphic identity - such as background patterns, headers, and footers - designed to make all materials instantly recognisable and visually consistent. These templates were widely used by all consortium partners to present their results and communicate about the project in a unified manner.

During the project’s course, a minor update was made to the templates following the name change of one partner from *RISE PROCESSUM* to **RISE**. All templates were subsequently updated to reflect this change, ensuring the continued accuracy and professionalism of the project’s communications. Additionally, a dedicated MainstreamBIO letterhead was created and used for formal documentation, including meeting agendas, workshop materials, and official communication during innovation events. These tools collectively reinforced the project’s identity and contributed to a coherent and professional image throughout its implementation.

Figure 9. MainstreamBIO's presentation template, cover (top) & content (bottom) pages

DX.Y: Deliverable name/ DDI/MM/YYYY

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRC-BIO-01-08
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
PROJECT NUMBER	101059420
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	XXXX
WORK PACKAGE	XXXX
TASK	XXXX
AUTHOR(S) (Organisation)	XXXX
REVIEWER(S)	XXXX
DATE	XXXX

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	X
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	X
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	X
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	X

Funded by the European Union

DX.Y: Deliverable name/ DDI/MM/YYYY

Executive Summary

1. LEVEL 1 TITLE

1.1 Level 2 title

1.1.1 Level 3 title

Level 4 title

Normal Text

Figure 1: <Figure title>

< Picture in table but without borders >

Table 1: <table title>

Category Level 1	Category Level 1	Category Level 1	Category Level 1
Category Level 2	Category Level 2	Category Level 2	Category Level 2
XX	XX	XX	XX
XX	XX	XX	XX

Funded by the European Union

Figure 10. MainstreamBIO's deliverable template, cover (top) & content (bottom) pages.

5.2.4 MainstreamBIO promotional video

As outlined in the updated version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan, MainstreamBIO's **promotional video** was produced and delivered by December 2023 (M15). Designed to appeal to a wide audience, the video plays a key role in increasing outreach through social media platforms, while also leveraging potential viral engagement. Since its release, the video has been made publicly available on [MainstreamBIO's YouTube channel](#), project website, and social media accounts (Facebook, X- former Twitter, LinkedIn). Given that several of the project's core concepts - such as bio-based solutions; the digital toolkit; MIPs; and innovation support services - may be unfamiliar to broader audiences, it was essential to present them in a clear, simple, and accessible format to promote understanding and encourage stakeholder involvement at the EU level. To date, the promotional video has received **1,300 views on the project's YouTube channel**.

The development of the video followed a structured three-phase process that ensured quality delivery while integrating feedback from consortium members. The initial step involved drafting the video script, including both narration and subtitles, which was then reviewed and refined in consultation with the consortium. This was followed by the creation of the video storyboard - outlining scene designs - which was shared with all partners for feedback. The final step involved producing the animated video, culminating in the official release on December 13th, 2023.

In terms of content and format, the video adopts a narrative approach, featuring animated characters who illustrate how small-scale bio-based solutions can be mainstreamed across seven rural EU regions. The inclusion of diverse characters reflects the project's inclusive and multi-actor orientation. The style was deliberately selected to make the project accessible and relatable, even for those unfamiliar with the bioeconomy. To enhance accessibility and widen its reach, English subtitles were added, ensuring engagement across the project's pilot regions as well as the broader international audience. A selection of screenshots from the video is presented in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11. MainstreamBIO's promotional video (screenshots)

5.3 Digital Presence

5.3.1 Website

The **MainstreamBIO website** has served as a central pillar of the project’s dissemination and communication strategy. As one of the project’s core digital tools, it has played a vital role in raising awareness, increasing visibility, and engaging stakeholders by presenting MainstreamBIO’s vision, actions, and progress to a broad audience. Officially launched by M4, the website was developed to function as an accessible and informative platform for both the public and project stakeholders, while also supporting effective communication within the consortium.

Designed using WordPress, the website offers a user-friendly interface that accommodates both the general public and technical audiences. It showcases key elements of the project - such as the concept; objectives; updates; publications; partner information and upcoming events - through a clear and intuitive layout. Additionally, the integration of Google Analytics has enabled ongoing monitoring of user engagement, visit frequency, and traffic sources, which has informed continuous improvements in content and usability throughout the project’s lifecycle.

The structure and content of the website have evolved to reflect the project’s progress, with dedicated sections added for initiatives such as the MainstreamBIO Open Call; success stories and project publications. These additions ensured that the platform remained relevant and informative, helping users stay connected with MainstreamBIO’s developments.

While this chapter provides key insights into the website’s role and engagement metrics as part of the broader D&C strategy, comprehensive details on the website’s structure, features, and technical implementation will be provided in Deliverable D5.8 “MainstreamBIO Web Portal – Final Version” (M35).

Figure 12. MainstreamBIO’s website” Homepage

The MainstreamBIO website hosts a wide range of content, including all publicly available project results; promotional materials; project deliverables and other relevant resources and links. In addition to presenting the project’s core vision and objectives; the website served as an entry point for visitors to learn more about the broader field of bioeconomy and bio-based solutions.

To ensure the website remained up-to-date and reflective of ongoing project developments, all consortium partners contributed relevant content and materials to support its creation, maintenance, and periodic updates. In this way, the platform not only provides timely information on MainstreamBIO’s actions and achievements but also offers insights into upcoming activities and opportunities for engagement throughout the project’s duration. The MainstreamBIO website URL is

<https://mainstreambio-project.eu/> and the contact email for the project is in line with it (info@mainstreambio-project.eu).

In the MainstreamBIO Consortium section, all 10 partners from 9 different European countries are presented. For each consortium partner is provided, information on their organization, website links but also the teams and individuals working behind the scenes of the MainstreamBIO project.

The website is structured around 9 pages (Home; About; Consortium; Advisory Board; Our Focal Regions; Open Call; MainstreamBIO Toolkit; Resources; News). For a better understanding of the project, the website provides pragmatic information on the project itself, its approach, its assets (what it brings to the table), and its consortium partners. Key information on each of the 7 MIPs is also provided including their specific needs and challenges. Additionally, the Open Call page, shares information on which initiatives/projects can apply to the different open calls listed to receive free of charge expert guidance in business and technical aspects to implement small-scale bio-based solutions in their region.

Figure 13. MainstreamBIO's website "Consortium"

Moreover, all MainstreamBIO project resources are openly accessible through the website - from promotional materials to deliverables and scientific publications. In parallel, the platform offers updates on the project's latest news and developments, including events; milestones; and partnerships, while also sharing relevant insights from the broader bioeconomy sector. To keep the MainstreamBIO community informed and engaged, the website has been updated on a weekly basis with articles highlighting recent project activities and achievements, as well as details about upcoming internal and external events via a regularly maintained event calendar.

Figure 14. MainstreamBIO's website "News – Projects News" page

Furthermore, the Open Call page was created displaying Open Calls in MainstreamBIO’s seven focal regions available for projects/initiatives implementing small-scale bio-based solutions. The webpage provides relevant information about the Open Call features, selection criteria, different services provided (technical and business), and the contact details of MainstreamBIO’s experts for each focal region.

Figure 15. MainstreamBIO's website "Open Call" page

During project’s duration, the Focal Regions webpage section was updated with detailed information for all 7 Multi-actor Innovation Platforms (MIPs). For each established MIP ([IE](#), [NL](#), [ES](#), [DK](#), [SE](#), [PL](#), [BG](#)) a subpage was created providing information on their needs and challenges including specificities of the region and services provided by MainstreamBIO.

Special attention was given to EU-funded related projects/initiatives with similar objectives to MainstreamBIO. To that end a dedicate section of the website was created for the “[Related Initiatives](#)”, providing information (description social media and website links) on the 15 established synergies up to August 2025.

A key improvement in the digital dissemination strategy during the second half of the project was the expansion of the “Resources” section on the MainstreamBIO website. In addition to the “[Deliverables](#)” subpage - created to host all public project deliverables in line with the Grant Agreement - two new sections were introduced to further support visibility and stakeholder engagement. The first, a “[Publications](#)” section, compiles all scientific publications produced within the scope of MainstreamBIO, offering easy access to peer-reviewed articles and conference papers. The second addition is the “[Audiovisual Material](#)” section, which hosts short videos presenting the MIPs and the supported cases across the seven pilot regions. These videos serve to highlight the practical application and local impact of bio-based innovations supported by the project. Each of these videos was uploaded on project’s YouTube channel; disseminated through the project's social media accounts and aligned with the project's broader objective to ensure that its results are openly accessible, clearly communicated, and tailored to a variety of target groups.

Table 6. MainstreamBIO Website Traffic

	Unique visits	Event Count	Sessions
Website traffic	8,719	67,538	14,087

Terminology explained:

- *User*: a user is a visitor who has initiated a session on your website
- *New User*: a visitor who has never been to your website before and is initiating their first session on your site
- *Event Count*: refers to the number of times an event is triggered on your website
- *Session*: refers to the set of actions taken by a user on your site in given time frame

Throughout the project's implementation, the MainstreamBIO website served as a central dissemination and engagement tool, with a total of **8,719 unique users**, 67,538 event counts, and 14,087 sessions recorded by the end of the project. While these numbers did not meet the initial M36 KPI target of more than 15,000 unique visits, the consortium took proactive steps to enhance performance in the second half of the project. In particular, the strategy was adapted to increase the frequency and relevance of content updates, including the publication of targeted articles, project news, and sector-related developments. This dynamic content approach, combined with continued promotion through social media and newsletters, significantly improved website visibility and user engagement. These efforts reflect a responsive and evolving digital communication strategy that aimed to maximise outreach and maintain stakeholder interest throughout the project lifecycle. To that end, several deeper engagement metrics were monitored through Google Analytics, highlighting how the MainstreamBIO website truly delivered value and impact over the past three years (Figure 16):

→ **25,364 total page views**, demonstrating that visitors stayed engaged to the website visiting it more than once.

→ **Top pages**: landing page (8,950 views); digital toolkit (1,506 views); open call (1,460 views), confirming that our most vital resources attracted sustained attention to those activities

→ **Global reach**: over 1,400 active users from the United States (and significant audiences in a many European countries) show that MainstreamBIO content resonated well beyond Europe.

→ High engagement with project's resources: More than **1,000 download material** (e.g., project reports and dissemination materials) underline the site's value as a free, go-to repository for project's network.

Beyond frequency, considerable emphasis was placed on promoting the website across multiple platforms, including coordinated social media campaigns and regular newsletters. These efforts significantly boosted both visibility and engagement, extending outreach well beyond the core regions. To ensure continued access and long-term benefit, the website and its open-access resources - such as publications, reports and other useful material - will remain active and publicly available for two years following the project's completion.

Figure 16. MainstreamBIO website google analytics screenshot

5.3.2 Newsletter

As part of its broader dissemination strategy, MainstreamBIO published a bi-annual newsletter to maintain consistent outreach and stakeholder engagement. By the end of the project, a total of six newsletters had been successfully published and made available through the project website. Each edition provided a concise yet comprehensive overview of MainstreamBIO's progress; upcoming actions and highlights from ongoing activities. The newsletter proved to be an effective complementary channel for stakeholder engagement, particularly for audiences less active on social media platforms or initially unfamiliar with the project. It served as a useful mechanism to maintain connection with a broader audience and encourage future engagement. While the responsibility for drafting and publishing the newsletter lay with WHITE, its success relied heavily on timely contributions from consortium partners, who were encouraged to share relevant updates and results to enrich the content and ensure a well-rounded representation of the project's developments. Below, short descriptions of each newsletter are provided, along with hyperlinks to access them via the project's website.

1st newsletter

The [first newsletter](#) introduced the project's overarching vision to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural Europe. It highlighted the launch of the Multi-actor Innovation Platforms (MIPs), the development of initial communication tools such as the project leaflet and website, and the creation of a catalogue of small-scale bio-based technologies and business models. This issue set the tone for the journey ahead, emphasising the importance of engaging local stakeholders and preparing the ground for tailored innovation support services.

2nd newsletter

The [second](#) one marked an important checkpoint in the project's first year. It showcased progress in establishing regional MIPs and outlined the early findings from stakeholder engagement and local needs assessments. A key highlight was the preparation for the 1st round of the MainstreamBIO Open Call, aiming to support real-life cases across the seven pilot regions. Updates on digital tools under development, as well as insights into events and collaborations with sister projects, were also featured—reflecting the project's growing network and impact.

3rd newsletter

The [3rd edition](#) of MainstreamBIO's bi-annual newsletter provided a comprehensive overview of the project's ongoing activities during the second year of implementation. It featured progress on the regional co-creation workshops that aimed to identify pathways for scaling up bio-based solutions. Additionally, it introduced the 2nd round of MainstreamBIO's Open Call, inviting new rural actors to benefit from tailored innovation support. Key updates on the Digital Toolkit and regional stakeholder

Figure 17. MainstreamBIO's 1st newsletter

engagement strategies were also highlighted, offering readers a deeper understanding of how the project continues to activate local bioeconomy ecosystems.

Figure 18. MainstreamBIO 2nd (left) and 3rd (right) newsletters

4th newsletter

The [4th newsletter](#) marked MainstreamBIO’s two-year anniversary, celebrating the project’s milestones while preparing for its final stages. This edition highlighted the successful setup and ongoing support of the Multi-actor Innovation Platforms (MIPs) and the progress of supported cases across the seven pilot regions. It also showcased success stories, outlined upcoming regional scale-up workshops, and provided insights into the mutual learning events that fostered knowledge exchange. Readers were also introduced to new promotional material and were reminded of the collaborative mission to embed small-scale bio-based solutions into rural communities.

5th newsletter

The [5th bi-annual newsletter](#) captured the momentum of the regional scale-up workshops conducted across Europe, summarising key lessons, stakeholder contributions, and early outcomes. It spotlighted the collaborative efforts of MIP leaders and partners to assess the scaling potential of bio-based solutions in rural settings. Alongside workshop updates, the newsletter provided a preview of the project’s final semester, including the upcoming policy roundtable and the final dissemination event in Brussels. This issue reinforced the project’s mission while inviting continued engagement from stakeholders and bioeconomy enthusiasts across the EU.

Figure 19. MainstreamBIO's 4th (left) and 5th (right) newsletters

6th newsletter

As MainstreamBIO's journey concluded in August 2025, our [6th newsletter](#) invited project's network to celebrate the inspiring progress we've made over the past three years in advancing small-scale bio-based solutions across rural Europe. Moreover updates from project final semester were shared, including MainstreamBIO's final dissemination event and the Joint Policy Paper "From Strategy to Action for a Regional, Participatory, and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy". This issue also offered a high level recap of our achievements and insights since 2022.

Figure 20. MainstreamBIO's 6th newsletter

Although the GA does not specify a KPI regarding the number of newsletter subscribers, efforts were consistently made throughout the project to attract and maintain a growing audience. By the end of the project (M36), MainstreamBIO's newsletter had reached a total of **76 subscribers**, reflecting steady and organic growth, with **6 newsletters officially published**. The newsletter successfully complemented other communication tools, helping to expand the project's outreach to stakeholders less active on social media and supporting long-term engagement.

Importantly, beyond its circulation to official subscribers, each edition of the newsletter was further disseminated through multiple channels to maximise visibility and accessibility. All newsletters were uploaded to the project website, allowing for easy access by visitors and encouraging additional readership beyond the initial mailing list. Furthermore, consortium partners actively supported outreach by sharing the newsletter links within their own networks, extending its reach across regions and stakeholder groups.

5.3.3 Social Media Accounts

In parallel with the launch of the MainstreamBIO website, dedicated social media accounts were established early in the project (M2) to expand outreach and promote the project's vision in real time. These platforms - YouTube, Facebook, X (former Twitter), and LinkedIn - served as powerful tools to raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and build a digital community around the project. Throughout the three-year implementation, SMAs played a central role in communicating updates, highlighting milestones, and sharing both internal achievements and relevant developments from the broader bioeconomy sector. By providing frequent and timely content, the project ensured continued visibility and engagement. All channels were actively maintained and updated on a weekly basis, fostering an online audience that extended the project's impact beyond the consortium. This consistent approach not only contributed to meeting MainstreamBIO's communication KPIs but also helped lay the foundation for sustaining engagement even after the project's completion.

Table 7. MainstreamBIO's Target Audience and Objectives

SMA	MAINSTREAMBIO Target Audience	Objectives
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers & farmer groups • Bio-based Industry • SMEs • Innovation Intermediaries • Policy advisors/makers • Academic community • Researchers • Civil society • NGOs • Financial institutions & investors • Other stakeholders • Standardisation & certification bodies • International organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Have a more institutional approach in order to boost professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest and possibly involve large corporations, more start-ups, innovation intermediaries and support networks
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomass producers • Farmers & farmer groups • Innovation Intermediaries • Policy advisors/makers • Academic community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Building a strong group of followers and exploiting the broader interests of that audience in relation to MainstreamBIO

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • NGOs • Other stakeholders • Standardisation & certification bodies • International organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Using of audio-visual promotional material to publicise the project
<p><u>X</u> [former Twitter]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs • Innovation Intermediaries • Policy advisors/makers • Civil society • Financial institutions & investors • Other stakeholders • Standardisation & certification bodies • International organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Enable the effective monitoring of developments and progress in other related projects and relevant organisations ✓ Steer attention towards the concepts and results of MainstreamBIO ✓ Identify opportunities for creating synergies with other similar initiatives
<p><u>YouTube</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs • Innovation Intermediaries • Academic community • Researchers • Civil society • NGOs • Financial institutions & investors • Other stakeholders • Standardisation & certification bodies • International organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to project's promotion via audio-visual mediums that is going to be made, in order to bring its viewers closer to the object and the faces of MainstreamBIO

WHITE was responsible for managing MainstreamBIO's social media accounts, while all consortium partners contributed to boosting the project's online presence by:

- Following and interacting with the project's official pages;
- Promoting MainstreamBIO's social media platforms within their own networks;
- Recommending relevant organisations and stakeholders for the project to engage with;
- Sharing sector-related news, articles, and developments to enrich the content stream;
- Disseminating MainstreamBIO updates through their institutional social media channels.

Encouraging partners to share and amplify the project's social media content played a critical role in increasing online visibility. By circulating important posts among the consortium; key messages; milestones and results reached a wider and more diverse audience. This coordinated effort helped strengthen engagement with external stakeholders and reinforced MainstreamBIO's digital footprint across Europe's rural bioeconomy community.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn emerged as the most impactful in terms of follower growth and stakeholder engagement. Created in M2, the project's LinkedIn page was strategically selected to reach a more professional and sector-specific audience. This platform offered direct access to a wide range of stakeholders - from bioeconomy experts and innovation intermediaries to academics, policymakers and industry actors - making it an ideal channel to promote MainstreamBIO's objectives; progress and outcomes.

Figure 21. MainstreamBIO's LinkedIn Profile

Throughout the project’s implementation, the LinkedIn page was consistently updated ,at a weekly basis, with project news/milestones; event announcements and sector-relevant insights. As a result, it recorded the highest follower count among all project social media accounts, validating the decision to leverage this platform for maximum visibility and knowledge exchange.

All consortium partners contributed to the success of the page by engaging with content, resharing updates within their own professional networks, and participating in knowledge-sharing discussions relevant to MainstreamBIO’s themes. The performance of the account was systematically monitored using LinkedIn analytics (Figure 23), helping WHITE track progress and refine the dissemination approach. The high engagement levels and steady growth in followers confirmed that LinkedIn was instrumental in amplifying the project’s message across Europe’s bioeconomy community.

Table 8. MainstreamBIO's LinkedIn analytics

	Posts' No.	Followers	Impressions	Reactions
LinkedIn posts	214	1,106	105,985	4,500

Figure 22. LinkedIn Impressions & Reactions analytics (2024-2025)

As of the time of drafting this deliverable, MainstreamBIO’s LinkedIn page has attracted 1,106 followers, demonstrating steady and meaningful engagement within the professional community. The platform served as a key avenue for connecting with a broad spectrum of stakeholders across the bioeconomy, including researchers, entrepreneurs, policy actors, and innovation intermediaries. To further support the long-term visibility of MainstreamBIO’s outcomes, the project actively contributed to the umbrella LinkedIn group of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA). This group has provided a shared space for continued interaction between bioeconomy-related projects and stakeholders, offering an opportunity to disseminate findings, post relevant articles or resources, announce sector-specific events, and keep the conversation alive on advancing sustainable, bio-based innovation in rural Europe.

Facebook

MainstreamBIO's Facebook page was created on M2 with the aim of developing a strong group of followers. This dissemination channel has been an excellent opportunity to promote the news and results resulting from MainstreamBIO among followers who are closest to project's subject and activities. Over the course of the project, the Facebook page effectively contributed to increasing awareness around bio-based innovations and rural bioeconomy practices. Specifically, the page served the following purposes:

- ➔ Acted as a hub for news and discussions, where content related to MainstreamBIO's core concepts and approaches was shared regularly;
- ➔ Provided timely updates on project progress; events; key activities and notable achievements;
- ➔ Engaged with citizens and key stakeholders by promoting participation in project activities such as workshops, pilots, and campaigns;
- ➔ Created linkages with other relevant groups, initiatives, and communities working in the field of bioeconomy and rural development;
- ➔ Functioned as an additional feedback channel, offering opportunities for interaction and input from followers.

Figure 23. MainstreamBIO Facebook profile

The monitoring of the account's performance were based on the metrics and insights provided by Facebook's analytics.

Figure 24. MainstreamBIO's Facebook analytics (2024-2025)

Table 9. MainstreamBIO Facebook analytics

	Posts No.	Impressions	Followers	Engagements
Facebook posts	154	5,010	76	1,494

Since its launch in M2, the MainstreamBIO Facebook page has played an important role in amplifying the project’s visibility and reaching a wider audience beyond its immediate network. Throughout the project's lifecycle, 154 posts were published, featuring updates on project milestones, partner activities, events, and bioeconomy-related news. As of Month 36, the page had gained a total of 76 followers, reflecting a steady growth in interest from stakeholders and the broader public. The total reach of the page exceeded 5,010 views, showcasing the page’s effectiveness in extending project content beyond direct followers through shares and organic engagement.

While LinkedIn has been MainstreamBIO’s primary channel for engaging with professionals and sector-specific audiences, the Facebook page proved particularly effective in complementing this effort by targeting civil society, individual consumers, and broader community groups. Its more accessible and casual nature allowed the project to reach users who may not be part of the rural or bioeconomy stakeholder ecosystem, but who are still key to promoting awareness and behavioural change. Therefore, despite showing comparatively lower engagement than LinkedIn in professional circles, Facebook successfully served its purpose in building awareness and expanding the project’s outreach into the general public domain.

X (former Twitter)

MainstreamBIO’s X (formerly Twitter) account was created in M2, becoming one of the core channels for real-time updates and quick dissemination of project-related news. From its early days, the platform allowed the project to remain connected with a broad digital community, including professionals, policy actors, and bioeconomy enthusiasts. The X account proved particularly useful during high-visibility activities, such as project-organised webinars and participation in external

events, where live updates helped expand reach and enhance audience engagement. The use of relevant hashtags enabled MainstreamBIO to position its messages within broader sectoral discussions and to attract the attention of stakeholders beyond the existing network.

Figure 25. MainstreamBIO's X profile

While not all consortium members had dedicated X accounts, those who did played an active role by regularly reposting MainstreamBIO's content, amplifying its visibility and contributing to a more vibrant digital presence. As of M36 the account had reached 164 followers and had shared more than 225 posts since launch.

To monitor the performance of the MainstreamBIO X account, built-in analytics tools were initially used to assess engagement, reach, and audience growth. However, following the platform's transition from Twitter to X, access to these analytics became limited. This shift has constrained the project's ability to track detailed performance indicators as previously possible. Despite this limitation, MainstreamBIO continued to maintain a regular posting schedule and monitored post interactions manually where feasible, ensuring that the platform remained an active part of the project's overall digital dissemination strategy.

Table 10. MainstreamBIO's X analytics

	Posts' No.	Followers
Twitter posts	225	164

YouTube channel

A dedicated YouTube channel was established in M2 as part of MainstreamBIO’s broader digital communication strategy. The channel served as the main hub for hosting all audiovisual content produced throughout the project’s lifecycle, playing a vital role in increasing the project’s visibility and engaging a wider audience through dynamic, accessible formats. While the platform primarily hosted MainstreamBIO promotional video, it also offered the potential for broader outreach through connections with other relevant channels, thereby expanding the project’s digital footprint.

Figure 26. MainstreamBIO's YouTube channel

Following the initial upload of the MainstreamBIO promotional video in December 2023 (M16) - which introduced the project’s vision; objectives and impact across rural Europe - the channel grew significantly in both content and strategic use. Over the course of the project, the channel was enriched with several important uploads, including:

- ✓ 6 webinars from the 1st awareness-raising campaign;
- ✓ 4 webinars from the 2nd awareness-raising campaign;
- ✓ 10 testimonial videos from the MIPs highlighting the project’s supported cases and scale-up cases.
- ✓ 1 instructions for MainstreamBIO’s Digital Toolkit

Table 11. MainstreamBIO YouTube channel analytics

	Views	Channel Subscribers
Promotional Video	1,300	31

In summary, the MainstreamBIO YouTube channel evolved into a key dissemination tool that effectively complemented written and visual communications, reinforcing project messaging in a format accessible to diverse stakeholder groups. MainstreamBIO's YouTube channel not only enhanced the visibility of project activities but also created a rich audiovisual archive documenting MainstreamBIO's engagement efforts, stakeholder experiences, and bio-based success stories. All videos were developed with active input from the consortium - partners contributed to scripting, local footage collection, and regional storytelling to ensure strong visual and narrative quality. WHITE coordinated the production and publication process, while all partners supported the development and recoding of them. As for the view of project's promotional video, a number of **1,300 exceeding the initial KPI of more than 500**.

6. Events

6.1 MainstreamBIO Events

Throughout its three-year journey, MainstreamBIO has actively organised and participated in a wide range of events aimed at promoting its vision, showcasing project outcomes, and strengthening its influence on the uptake of small-scale bio-based solutions across rural Europe. These events served as key moments to connect with local and international stakeholders, present innovative tools and findings, and engage in meaningful exchanges around the future of the bioeconomy. By leveraging both internal project events and external opportunities - such as workshops; webinars and thematic roundtables - MainstreamBIO significantly amplified its visibility, built strategic partnerships, and contributed to ongoing discussions on sustainable development, circular economy, and rural innovation within the bio-based sector.

Internal events

Co-creation workshops (Task 2.3): Seven co-creation workshops, one for each MIP, were organised between May and June 2023 by consortium partners (INNV, MTU, AUP, IUNG, WR, PROC, and FBCD). The workshops aimed to develop innovative support services (business and technological) for key rural actors in the bio-based value chain and actively involve them in shaping the service portfolio for each MIP. INNV coordinated the workshops while, WHITE was responsible for the co-creation of guidelines. In total, the co-creation workshops engaged 92 stakeholders.

Figure 27. MainstreamBIO's Co-creation Workshops

Capacity building workshops (Task 3.2): Each MIP successfully organised a capacity building workshop aimed at equipping farmers, producers, and local actors in the agricultural and forestry sectors with the knowledge needed to engage with the project’s innovation support services. These sessions provided practical coaching to help stakeholders understand how to effectively navigate and utilise MainstreamBIO’s digital toolkit. By M28, all 7 capacity-building workshops had been successfully conducted, engaging a total of 160 stakeholders.

Figure 28. MainstreamBIO's Capacity Building Workshops

Networking events and Demo days (Task 3.4): By M36, each MIP successfully implemented two rounds of networking events and one demo day, bringing stakeholders together to establish meaningful connections between MainstreamBIO-supported multi-actor partnerships and relevant actors across the regional bioeconomy landscape. These events served not only as a platform to showcase local innovations and bio-based solutions but also as a catalyst to inspire further engagement, encouraging additional stakeholders to explore opportunities within the bioeconomy. In total, 14 networking events and 7 demo days were held, bringing together 368 stakeholders.

Figure 29. MainstreamBIO's Networking Events

Awareness raising and educational events (Task 3.5): MainstreamBIO successfully implemented two local awareness-raising and education campaigns in each MIP, one per innovation round. These campaigns aimed to inform and engage local communities around the bioeconomy and small-scale bio-based solutions. Across both rounds, a total of 10 webinars and 14 in-person events were carried out, providing a dynamic mix of knowledge-sharing formats. These efforts engaged 1220 stakeholders, enhancing understanding, fostering dialogue and encouraging wider participation in regional bioeconomy activities.

Figure 30. MainstreamBIO's Webinars

Figure 31. MainstreamBIO's in-person events

Scale-up workshops (Task 4.2): By M30, MainstreamBIO successfully conducted 7 scale-up workshops across all participating regions, playing a central role in advancing the project's core objective of mainstreaming small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. Through open dialogue and co-creation sessions, participants exchanged insights gained during their engagement with the project, mapped common barriers, and proposed viable business model pathways for scaling up bio-based initiatives. A total number of 161 participants was reached in these events.

Figure 32. MainstreamBIO's Scale-up Workshops

Mutual Learning workshops (Task 4.3): Seven cross-regional mutual learning workshops - including field visits - were successfully organised by April 2025, providing a structured setting for international exchange and peer-to-peer learning among rural bioeconomy stakeholders. Hosted by each MIP and coordinated by FBCD, these workshops brought together 130 representatives from regional initiatives and linked networks to share best practices, explore innovative business models, and discuss nutrient recycling strategies. Field missions enabled participants to visit real-life deployment sites of small-scale bio-based solutions, supporting hands-on engagement and direct dialogue with solution providers.

Figure 33. MainstreamBIO's Mutual Learning Workshops

Policy roundtable (Task 4.4): MainstreamBIO Policy Roundtable took place on May 14th, 2025, in Brussels, under the framework of the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference (EuRCBC) joint event. Organised by IUNG with support from all partners, the roundtable aimed to present and discuss initial policy insights and the draft version of the Replication Guide and Toolkit, developed based on findings from WP1, WP2, and implementation experiences from Tasks 4.1 to 4.3. The event gathered 27 stakeholders from EU institutions, regional policymakers, and bioeconomy actors to exchange on practical and strategic pathways for supporting the mainstreaming of small-scale bio-based solutions in rural Europe.

Figure 34. MainstreamBIO's policy roundtable

Final dissemination event (Task 5.1): MainstreamBIO’s final dissemination event was successfully held on May 14th, 2025, in Brussels, within the framework of the EuRCBC. The event was co-organised with ROBIN and SCALE-UP projects, creating a joint platform to amplify outreach and visibility. As the opening day of the EuRCBC, the final event highlighted the diverse perspectives and practical tools that enable local communities, businesses, and policymakers to adopt and scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. Through presentations of real-world success stories and project results, the event inspired 145 participants by showcasing tangible progress and impact achieved on the ground. Further details on MainstreamBIO’s final event can be found in Chapter 7 of this deliverable.

Figure 35. MainstreamBIO's Final Dissemination Event

Table 12 provides an overview of MainstreamBIO’s internal events, along with the corresponding engagement metrics achieved:

Table 12. MainstreamBIO's internal events.

Event	Task	No. of events	No. of participants	Status	Deliverable
Co-creation workshops	2.3	7	92	Completed	D2.3
Capacity building workshops	3.2	7	160	Completed	D3.1; D3.3
Networking & Demo events	3.4	21	366	Completed	

Event	Task	No. of events	No. of participants	Status	Deliverable
In-person events	3.5	14	760	Completed	D3.2
Webinars	3.5	10	455	Completed	
Scale-up workshops	4.2	7	161	Completed	D4.2
Mutual-learning workshops	4.3	7	130	Completed	
Policy roundtable	4.4	1	27	Completed	D4.8
Final dissemination event	5.1	1	145	Completed	D5.3
Total		75	2,296	-	-

Given the diverse nature and varying formats of the internal events organised under MainstreamBIO, the tracking of stakeholder participation has been approached in a flexible yet consistent manner. While some events followed a structured format with formal registration processes, others were designed as more dynamic and interactive engagements, making exact participant categorisation more complex. Nonetheless, the consortium made a concerted effort to involve a wide range of relevant stakeholder groups across the bioeconomy landscape - including rural actors, rural industry, academia, policy actors and civil society - ensuring that each activity was aligned with the project's objectives of inclusivity and stakeholder relevance. The table presented below reflect a consolidated overview of participation, offering a general mapping of stakeholder engagement per group, based on the best available data collected during the project.

Table 13. Stakeholder group engagement in MainstreamBIO internal events

Stakeholder Group/Event ¹	CCW	CBW	NDE	IPE ²	WEB	SUP	MLW	PR	FDE
<i>Rura/Bioeconomy Actors</i>	23	88	197		27	29	37	1	16
<i>Industry/Tech/Business</i>	16	7	99		65	60	48	6	66
<i>Research/Academia</i>	24	48	46		243	46	40	11	32
<i>Policy Actors</i>	11	2	10		31	8	-	8	27

¹ CCW: Co-creation Workshops | CBW: Capacity Building Workshops | NDE: Networking & Demo Events | IPE: In-person Events | WEB: Webinars | SUP: Scale-up Workshops | MLW: Mutual Learning Workshops | PR: Policy Roundtable | FDE: Final Dissemination Event

² Due to the dynamic nature of the in-person events and the high level of engagement they had, detailed tracking of the participating stakeholder groups was not feasible. Nevertheless, as reported in D3.4, the events successfully attracted a diverse range of stakeholders, including academic institutions, biomass producers, industry actors, civil society organisations, agri-business representatives, and policymakers.

General Public/ Community Initiatives	9	-	3		46	15	5	1	4
Other	9	15	11		23	3	-	-	-
Total	92	160	366		455	161	130	27	145

The distribution of stakeholder groups engaged in MainstreamBIO's internal events is illustrated in the pie chart below (Figure 37). Throughout the project, efforts were made to promote gender inclusivity and support female participation in the bioeconomy. This commitment was reflected in targeted actions, such as the dedicated webinar on "[Women Industrial Leaders in Agriculture, Marine Beauty, and Bio-based Fashion Textiles](#)" held during the second round of MainstreamBIO's webinar series.

Figure 36. Stakeholder groups distribution engaged in MainstreamBIO's events

MainstreamBIO's internal events proved to be instrumental in building awareness; building collaboration, and advancing the uptake of small-scale bio-based solutions across the project's seven regions, actively engaging **2,296 stakeholders**. These **75 activities**, ranging from co-creation and capacity-building workshops to policy roundtables and mutual learning missions, successfully mobilised stakeholders, stimulated dialogue, and reinforced knowledge exchange. The strong participation numbers and the broad spectrum of topics covered reflect the project's inclusive and hands-on approach to stakeholder engagement. By aligning event objectives with project goals and tailoring each activity to local contexts, MainstreamBIO maximised its outreach and laid the groundwork for continued engagement beyond the project's lifecycle.

6.2 External conferences and events

Throughout the three-year implementation of MainstreamBIO, the consortium actively participated in a wide range of external events and conferences at both EU and national levels. In line with the goals originally outlined in the first version of the DCP, these participations allowed the consortium to:

- Present MainstreamBIO's concept, objectives, and methodology.
- Showcase project results and success stories from the field.

- Promote awareness-raising and stakeholder engagement actions.
- Strengthen collaborations and explore synergies with related initiatives.
- Attract relevant stakeholders to engage in project activities (e.g. MIPs; innovation services; digital toolkit etc.).
- Disseminate project materials and raise visibility of communication channels (website, SMAs, newsletter).
- Stay informed on emerging trends and policy developments within the bioeconomy sector

These external engagements played a crucial role in expanding MainstreamBIO’s outreach, facilitating peer learning, and reinforcing its presence in the broader bioeconomy community. They also offered a platform for two-way knowledge exchange, enabling the project to contribute to ongoing sectoral discussions while gathering insights to improve its activities. This final version of the DCP includes a detailed list of the external events attended by consortium members. All partners were encouraged to use the project’s official visual identity and communication materials (e.g. leaflet, poster, presentation templates) during their participations and to complete the external event reporting template (Annex 4) for internal monitoring and assessment.

Table 14. MainstreamBIO's external events attended

#	Event	Type of event	Locations	When
1	“Projects2Projects” Mobilisation and Mutual learning workshop	Workshop	Brussels, BE	05/10/2022
2	AGRA 2023	Exhibition	Plovdiv, BG	22/02/2023
3	Go-Grass final conference	Final Conference	Brussels, BE	12/03/2023
4	CAPBIO4BG project workshop	Workshop	Plovdiv, BG	19/04/2023
5	COOPID Final Event	Final Conference	Brussels, BE	31/05/2023
6	European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	Conference/Exhibition	Bologna, IT	06/08/2023
7	EXPOBIOMASA	Exhibition	Valladolid, ES	05/09/2023
8	National Ploughing Championships of Ireland	Exhibition	Portlaoise, IL	21/09/2023
9	Regional Innovation Valleys for Bioeconomy and Food Systems in Europe	EC event	Plovdiv, BG	13/10/2023
10	EIT Food high-level conference "The Future of Food"	Conference	Brussels, BE	26/10/2023
11	Bioeconomy Forum from Castilla y León	Exhibition & Networking event	Soria, ES	26/10/2023

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12	Circular Bioeconomy Forum in Seville	Exhibition & Networking event	Sevilla, ES	21/11/2023
13	Clusters Meet Regions	Exhibition & Networking event	Iasi, RO	21-23/11/2023
14	Agriloop Project Monthly Meeting	Project meeting	Online	24/11/2023
15	Better Farming Awards	Exhibition & Networking event	Killenard, IL	30/11/2023
16	OLEAF4VALUE Stakeholder meeting	Stakeholder meeting	Madrid, ES	30/01/2024
17	BIC Matchmaking event	Matchmaking event	Brussels, BE	08/02/2024
18	Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival main event	Festival & Networking event	Brussels, BE	13-14/03/2024
19	Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival , Thessaloniki satellite event	Festival & Networking event	Thessaloniki, GR	14/03/2024
20	CBE-JU, BIC, CEE2ACT - Promoting Bioeconomy in Greece	Knowledge Exchange & Networking event	Athens, GR	15/04/2024
21	Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference	Conference	Örnsköldsvik, SE	25/04/2024
22	ROBIN Stakeholders Engagement Event (Region of Central Macedonia; Greece)	Exhibition & Networking event	Thessaloniki, GR	29/05/2024
23	BBioNets project cross-fertilisation meeting	Meeting	Online	29/05/2024
24	XX European Rural Development Network Conference “Green transformation in the European rural areas”	Conference	Vilnius, LI	11-13/09/2024
25	Rural Pact Support Office – Policy Action Lab	Knowledge Exchange event	Online	19/09/2024
26	IV Summit of Polish Operation Groups in Łódź	Conference	Warsaw, Poland	5-7/11/2024
27	Biorcircular Summit	Conference	Madrid, Spain	11/02/2025
28	3-CO webinar	Webinar	Online	25/03/2025
29	EXPOBIOMASA	Conference	Valladolid, Spain	07/05/2025
30	EU Green Week’s “Accelerating the circular bioeconomy: innovation for sustainable rural development”	Conference	Online	01/06/2025

Below representative photos are illustrated showcasing MainstreamBIO’s participation in various external events.

Figure 37. Representative photos from MainstreamBIO's participation in external events

By the end of the project, consortium partners participated in a total of **30 external events**, actively promoting MainstreamBIO's vision; activities and results. To ensure consistent representation, all partners had access to a full suite of promotional materials. These tools helped maintain a coherent and professional visual identity across all dissemination activities. Presentations delivered at external events adhered to the project's communication guidelines and were aligned with the core messaging and objectives of MainstreamBIO. In preparation for external engagements, partners informed WHITE in advance, allowing for coordinated promotion through the project's digital channels. This helped maximise visibility and audience engagement. After participating as speakers; panellists, or organisers, partners were asked to complete the Event Reporting Template ([Annex 4: External Events Reporting Template](#)), enabling the project to systematically document dissemination actions and assess their contribution to the overall communication strategy.

7. Final dissemination event

The final dissemination event of MainstreamBIO was held on 14 May 2025 in Brussels, as part of the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference (EuRCBC). This two-day event brought together six Horizon Europe projects - [MainstreamBIO](#), [ROBIN](#), [SCALE-UP](#), [BioRural](#), [BIOMODEL4REGIONS](#), and [RuralBioUP](#) - under the shared framework of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA). It served as both a peak point of the project's communication and engagement activities and a key opportunity for MainstreamBIO to position its outcomes within the broader European bioeconomy landscape. In preparation for the event, RBA partners designed a common visual identity for the event, establishing a consistent look and presence across all communication materials including a logo, banner, and a presentation template (Fig. 38). This visual coherence reinforced the collective visibility of the participating projects and enhanced recognition throughout the conference. The preparation phase also involved collaborative agenda planning, alignment of communication goals, and the development of shared promotional narratives to effectively present the breadth of rural bioeconomy initiatives showcased at the event.

Figure 38. EuRCBC visual identity

Hosted at Comet Louise, the conference brought together a **diverse group of 145 stakeholders**, including EU officials, regional policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and members of civil society. MainstreamBIO's final dissemination event was strategically embedded within the first day of the conference, allowing the project to contribute to and benefit from a broader dialogue on policy and innovation. The first day opened with two keynote speeches delivered by Michael Losch, Coordinator for Bioeconomy at the European Commission, and Marci Rupp from the Biobased Industries Consortium. These were followed by a dynamic fire-pitching session in which each of the hosting projects briefly presented its scope, methodology, and core achievements. The day then continued with interactive sessions, including a panel discussion on "Diverse Perspectives on Bioeconomy," a presentation session titled "Tools for Advancing the EU's Bioeconomy," and a concluding panel showcasing the success stories of various EU-funded projects.

Figure 39. EuRCBC 1st day insights

The second day began with a keynote speech by Mr. Calikowski from DG Research and Innovation (European Commission) on the topic “Pathway Towards the New EU Bioeconomy Strategy.” This was followed by a joint session presenting policy reflections and lessons learned from MainstreamBIO and its sister projects. The aim was to highlight shared challenges and propose coordinated policy recommendations, paving the way for deeper alignment with EU strategies and funding frameworks. A key highlight was MainstreamBIO’s dedicated policy roundtable, organised under Task 4.4, titled “Implementation of Small-scale BIO-based Solutions Across Rural Europe.” Drawing on the project’s research, pilot activities, and stakeholder engagement, the session explored institutional, regulatory, and market factors affecting the scaling and replication of bio-based innovations. It also served as a platform to present and collect feedback on the project’s Replication Guide and Toolkit, developed through iterative work with regional stakeholders and validated during mutual learning activities across the seven pilot regions.

Figure 40. EuRCBC 2nd day - Joint Policy Brief (left) and Policy Roundtable sessions (right)

Running in parallel with the policy roundtable were two additional sessions: ROBIN's Train-the-Trainer Workshop and the International Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop "Building Bridges in Bioeconomy," jointly organised by RuralBioUP and BIOMODEL4REGIONS.

Figure 41. Marketplace (top) and ToT (bottom) session of the 2nd day

The detailed agenda of EuRCBC has been included in Annex 6: EuRBC Agenda

Embedding MainstreamBIO's final dissemination event within the framework of the EuRCBC was a carefully considered strategic decision that significantly enhanced the project's visibility, impact, and outreach. Rather than opting for a standalone event, we chose to co-organise a high-level joint conference alongside complementary EU-funded projects. This collaborative approach not only maximised logistical and communication synergies but also positioned MainstreamBIO within a broader policy and stakeholder dialogue, enabling meaningful cross-project exchange and amplifying the project's voice in key discussions. From conceptual planning to execution, the organisational process required sustained coordination among multiple consortia, alignment on thematic priorities, and active engagement to co-design sessions that reflected shared challenges and ambitions. The outcome was a dynamic, well-attended event that reached far beyond the immediate project network, serving as a platform for knowledge transfer; stakeholder interaction and forward-looking policy reflection.

8. Publications

Since the very beginning of MainstreamBIO, partners were actively encouraged to disseminate key project findings and outcomes through scientific publications. These publications represent one of the most valuable outputs of the project, as they capture and preserve the new knowledge generated through the support and development of small-scale bio-based solutions, innovative business models, and social innovations. According to the dissemination strategy, a minimum of three open-access publications in peer-reviewed journals was set as a key target. Beyond this, partners were welcomed to propose and pursue additional publications that could further amplify the visibility and impact of MainstreamBIO's achievements.

The following table provides a detailed overview of all publications produced within the framework of MainstreamBIO, highlighting the title; date and responsible partner for each publication:

Table 15. MainstreamBIO's publications

Title	Journal/Event	Leading Author	Date	Link
<i>Understanding the biomass availability, flows and value chains of diverse rural regions in Europe</i>	<i>31st European Biomass Conference & Exhibition</i>	MTU	June, 2023	Link
<i>Multi-actor Innovation Platforms MAINSTREAMing small-scale BIO-based solutions across rural Europe</i>	<i>Green transformation in the European rural areas</i>	IUNG	September, 2024	Link
<i>Digital tools in the bioeconomy</i>	<i>AAIC 2024, Association for the Advancement of Industrial Crops</i>	IUNG	September, 2024	Link
<i>Small-scale bio-based solutions promoting the regional development of bioeconomy</i>	<i>Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference (NWBC)</i>	RISE	October, 2024	Link
<i>MainstreamBIO conceptual poster</i>	<i>Bio Circular SUMMIT 2025</i>	INNV	February, 2025	Link
<i>Understanding the biomass availability, flows and value chains of diverse rural regions in Europe.</i>	<i>Research to Impact Showcase Event</i>	MTU	April, 2025	Link
<i>From local innovations to global markets in the forestry bioeconomy</i>	<i>EU CAP Network</i>	QPLAN	April, 2025	Link
<i>From Strategy to Action for a Regional, Participatory, and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy</i>	<i>Joint Policy Paper</i>	MainstreamBIO; BIORural; RuralBIOUp; SCALE-UP	June, 2025	Link

MainstreamBIO has successfully delivered a total of **8 scientific publications**, exceeding the original KPI of three. These outputs reflect the strong engagement of partners in sharing project-generated knowledge with the broader academic, policy, and practitioner communities. The publications addressed key themes of the project, such as regional biomass value chains, innovation platforms, and digital tools for the bioeconomy. By publishing in relevant conferences and peer-reviewed forums, MainstreamBIO not only broadened its visibility but also contributed valuable insights to ongoing discussions around sustainable rural development and bio-based innovation.

9. Networking and established synergies

Leveraging networks and communication multipliers has been a cornerstone of MainstreamBIO's dissemination and communication strategy. From the beginning of it, the project prioritised building connections with high-impact initiatives, relevant scientific communities, and key stakeholder groups. Establishing [synergies](#) - particularly with other EU-funded projects - significantly enhanced the visibility of MainstreamBIO's actions and results by broadening its outreach and strengthening its relevance within the European bioeconomy ecosystem.

Throughout the project's lifecycle, MainstreamBIO actively pursued joint dissemination activities with clustered and sister projects. These collaborations included co-developing and promoting shared promotional materials; participating in and co-organising joint events and inviting external initiatives to participate in MainstreamBIO's activities such as workshops and campaigns. Furthermore, the project supported EC-driven efforts to increase cross-project collaboration and visibility within Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 communities.

Collaboration took various practical forms, including:

- Mutual referencing of project websites and digital platforms;
- Cross-promotion through official social media channels;
- Exchange of news results; event invitations and press releases;
- Participation in and co-organisation of joint events and webinars;
- Contribution of relevant materials to the MainstreamBIO digital toolkit;
- Inviting representatives from other projects to MainstreamBIO-led events and workshops.

An updated list of EU-funded projects and initiatives that synergised with MainstreamBIO is provided in Table 16. Regular and open communication with these projects ensured mutual support, facilitated knowledge transfer and enabled the identification of new opportunities for joint action.

Table 16. Established synergies

Synergy Project	Description	Website
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATION FOR BIOBASED SYSTEMS	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is a 3-year EU – funded project that aims to assess and promote the adoption of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability of the products along the EU and international value chains and trades.	Link
RuralBioUp <i>Empowering EU Rural Regions to scale-Up and adopt small-scale Bio-based solutions</i>	RuralBioUp main objective is to support innovators to scale-up inclusive and small-scale biobased solutions in rural areas, through the creation of a favourable ecosystem to be maintained within the empowered regions and transferred to other ones, in order to contribute to regional, urban and consumer-based transitions towards a sustainable, regenerative, inclusive and just circular economy and bioeconomy across all regions of Europe.	Link
SCALE-UP	The overall aim of the SCALE-UP project is to adapt, implement and evaluate tools to help regional actors to overcome the	Link

<i>Community Driven Bioeconomy Development</i>	apparent bottlenecks towards fully exploiting bioeconomy potentials in their region. trades.	
BioRural <i>Connecting the dots to unlock the potential of European rural areas towards a circular Bioeconomy</i>	BioRural is a project that seeks to bridge the gap between bio-based innovations and European citizens' everyday life. It involves 19 partners from 14 countries and aims to create a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. An online toolkit will be generated to provide support to stakeholders in the development, scaling and mainstreaming of Bioeconomy ideas and initiatives. Eight success stories have already been identified and integrated into BioRural.	Link
ShapingBio <i>The bioeconomy of the future</i>	ShapingBio aims to provide evidence-based and concrete information and recommendations for better policy alignment and stakeholder actions to realise the cross-sectoral potential of the bioeconomy and to reduce the fragmentation across bio-based sectors and food system and policies across regions, domains and governance levels.	Link
ROBIN <i>Deploying circular bioeconomies at a regional level with a territorial approach</i>	ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.	Link
ALFA <i>Upscaling the market uptake of renewable energy by unlocking the biogas potential of livestock farming</i>	ALFA is set on unlocking the potential of biogas production from livestock farming to enhance the wider uptake of RES and increase the share of bioenergy as a baseload energy source while ensuring reduced emissions from untreated manure and supporting the creation of new jobs and revenue for the livestock farming industry.	Link
3-CO <i>Enabling sustainable consumption performance and competitiveness</i>	The supportive framework that will be developed in 3-CO includes actionable guidelines for label design for label and certification schemes owners that reflect consumers' and other stakeholders' needs, digital solutions to support better-informed decision-making processes of consumers as well as policy recommendations on deploying social measures.	Link
Model2Bio <i>Transforming waste into feedstock</i>	Model2Bio is developing a Decision-Support Tool based on mathematical models, able to predict the physical-chemical characteristics of agri-food residual streams and their best valorising route. The project explores the potential for resource and energy recovery of each valorisation route, taking into account seasonality and geographical location. It will be tested and validated for sectors as meat, vegetable, dairy and alcoholic beverages in Spain, Belgium/Netherlands and Greece.	Link
AgriLoop	The AgriLoop project will develop safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) bioconversion processes and integrate them into a cascading biorefinery approach, to convert agri-residues	Link

<p><i>Converting agri-food residues into high-value products</i></p>	<p>from tomato, soy, straw, potato, brewery, oil, winery and livestock sectors, among others, into plant and microbial proteins, polyesters and other bio-based chemicals. AgriLoop strengthens EU-China cooperation, inform SSbD guidance and increase resource efficiency through reduced discharges of agricultural residues.</p>	
<p>BRILIAN <i>Circular Future for Rural Areas</i></p>	<p>BRILIAN has been conceived to support the adoption of sustainable, cooperative business models in rural areas and enable a better transition to bio-based economies, playing a pivotal role in revitalising these regions and fostering sustainable economic and social development, making primary producers active members of the supply chain.</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>RIBES <i>Regional Inclusive Biobased Entrepreneurship Solutions</i></p>	<p>The RIBES project (Regional Inclusive Biobased Entrepreneurship Solutions) aims to accelerate the adoption of bio-based innovations by developing governance and business models that integrate the principles of the circular bioeconomy, social innovation, and rural development. Focused on nine European regions, RIBES fosters collaboration among policymakers, businesses, academia, and civil society to create sustainable and inclusive bio-based value chains. By promoting stakeholder engagement and innovative practices, the project contributes to building resilient rural economies and advancing the European bioeconomy agenda</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>BIO2REG <i>Enabling transition towards circular and systemic BIOeconomy model regions by a Regions-to-Regions approach</i></p>	<p>BIO2REG is a three-year European project that aims to enable the systemic transformation of greenhouse gas-intensive regions into bioeconomy model regions. Nine partners are committed to developing concrete measures to enable sustainable bioeconomic transitions in European regions.</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>DIVAGRI <i>Revenue diversification pathways in Africa through bio-based and circular agricultural innovations</i></p>	<p>The DIVAGRI project proposes a wide range of bio-based innovative solutions adapted to specific conditions in target countries. Ecosystem restoration in combination with diverse crop production in regenerative agricultural systems, mobile biorefineries for biomass conversion to high-value compounds and bioenergy, and the highly innovative clay-based micro-irrigation system “SLECI” (Self-regulating, Low Energy, Claybased Irrigation) are solutions developed by DIVAGRI.</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>BIOMODEL4REGIONS <i>Supporting the establishment of the innovative governance models to achieve better informed decision-making processes, social engagement and innovation in the bio-based economy.</i></p>	<p>The BIOMODEL4REGIONS project aims to support the establishment of the innovative governance models at local/regional level to achieve better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement and innovation to support and strengthen EU and international science-policy interfaces to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.</p>	<p>Link</p>

Joint activities with sister projects

MainstreamBIO established a strong collaborative relationship with its sister projects funded under the same Horizon Europe call - [RuralBioUP](#), [BioRural](#), and [SCALE-UP](#) - reinforcing a shared commitment to advancing rural bioeconomy development across Europe. Throughout the project lifecycle, the sister projects engaged in regular coordination meetings to share insights, align dissemination efforts and exchange good practices, particularly around the development of digital tools and stakeholder engagement strategies. One of the most significant outcomes of this collaboration was the joint authorship of the policy paper titled [“From Strategy to Action for a Regional, Participatory, and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy”](#). This document consolidates shared lessons and recommendations from the Joint Policy Observations Session, that was co-organised by all sister projects under the EuRCBC, into a unified policy voice, gaining visibility at both EU and national levels.

The sister projects also joined forces to **organise and co-host the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference**, this flagship event that showcased project results, hosted interactive session and supported stakeholder networking. Additionally, the **MainstreamBIO policy roundtable was strengthened by active participation** and input from RuralBioUP, BioRural, and SCALE-UP, further cementing the cooperative spirit among the projects. The projects’ cooperation extended beyond policy and events. The sister projects actively **coordinated and established the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance**, a shared platform for amplifying the voice of rural bioeconomy stakeholders which is better described in the following section. Sister projects also had **coordinated participation in external events**, such as the [Clusters Meet Regions International Conference](#) (organized by the European Cluster Collaboration Platform) and supported one another's internal events and communication campaigns through cross-promotion and shared visibility channels.

Indicative photos of the above mentioned activities are presented below.

Figure 42. Joint activities with sister projects

Rural Bioeconomy Alliance

In parallel with the establishment of synergies with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives, MainstreamBIO was amongst the projects that established the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance during May, 2023. The **Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)** is a cluster of European-funded projects aimed at accelerating and supporting the development of circular rural Bioeconomy initiatives in the EU. Up to August, 2025, 20 EU-funded projects are involved in the RBA. With a focus on rural sustainable circular bioeconomy initiatives, the RBA investigates, develops and analyses success stories, best practices, pilots, including ways to increase the adoption of circular bioeconomy concepts, mainly in rural areas. The goal of the cluster is to speed up growth of bioeconomy by sharing knowledge on project outcomes and supporting dissemination and communication activities related to the existing knowledge of bioeconomy.

The RBA continues to attract increasing interest from projects eager to join its collaborative efforts, ensuring the long-term sustainability of this after the funding projects' completion. Through regular meetings, RBA members stay updated on the latest news and developments from each participating project, fostering a dynamic exchange of insights and resources. Notably, the alliance actively engages in events such as:

- the Regional Innovation Valleys for Bioeconomy and Food Systems in Europe (Bulgaria, October 2023)
- the Annual World Circular Economy Forum (WCEF) (Brussels, April 2024)
- the Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival (Brussels, March 2024)

thus, further enhancing opportunities for synergistic partnerships and collective advancement in the bioeconomy sector.

Figure 43. RBA's logo

Figure 44. RBA's & MainstreamBIO's participation in Regional Innovation Valleys for Bioeconomy and Food Systems in Europe (Oct. 2023, Bulgaria)

Beyond serving as a platform for knowledge exchange and mutual support among EU-funded projects, the RBA played a critical role in elevating collaboration to a new level. The RBA became the foundation for co-organising the first **European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference (EuRCBC)** - a landmark joint event led by six member projects. This conference not only marked a milestone in the RBA's activities but also provided the framework for MainstreamBIO's **final**

dissemination event, as outlined in Chapter 7 of this deliverable. As such, the RBA has proven to be instrumental in transforming shared goals into collective action, amplifying the visibility; impact, and legacy of its member projects.

Overview of joint activities with clustered projects

In line with its commitment to building strong alliances, MainstreamBIO actively engaged in collaborative actions with clustered projects sharing similar goals in advancing the rural bioeconomy and supporting small-scale bio-based innovations. These joint activities served as key enablers for cross-project learning, broader outreach, and the co-promotion of impactful outcomes. The following table highlights the main joint activities undertaken in collaboration with clustered projects throughout the project's duration.

Table 17. MainstreamBIO's joint activities with clustered projects

Activity	Qty.	Related project	Link
MainstreamBIO's presentation in AgriLoop Project Meeting	1	AgriLoop	Link
MainstreamBIO's participation in Clusters Meet Regions Conference	1	MainstreamBIO; RuralBioUP; BioRural; SCALE-UP	Link
MainstreamBIO's participation at Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival Satellite Event	1	ROBIN; BioGov.net; GenB	Link
Participation of Bio4Africa Project representatives in MainstreamBIO's in Mutual Learning Workshop in Lelystad, Netherlands	1	Bio4Africa	Link
Participation of BIOMODEL4REGIONS Project representatives in MainstreamBIO's Mutual Learning Workshop in Sweden	1	BIOMODEL4REGIONS	Link
MainstreamBIO's participation in 3-CO webinar	1	3-CO	N/A
MainstreamBIO's final event under the EuRCBC	1	MainstreamBIO; ROBIN; SCALE-UP	Link
MainstreamBIO;s policy roundtable organised under the EuRCBC	1	MainstreamBIO; RuralBioUp; BioRural; SCALE-UP; ROBIN; BIOMODEL4REGIONS	Link
Presentation of joint policy observations from RuralBioUp, MainstreamBio, SCALE-UP and BioRural during the EuRCBC	1	MainstreamBIO; RuralBioUp; SCALE-UP; BioRural	N/A
Development of "From Strategy to Action for a Regional, Participatory, and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy" (Joint Policy Paper)	1	MainstreamBIO; RuralBioUp; SCALE-UP; BioRural	Link
RBA establishment	1	BioRural; MainstreamBIO; P2Green; RELIEF; RuralBioUp;	Link

		SCALE-UP; COOPID; BioModel4Regions; ShapingBio; CEE2ACT; ROBIN.	
RBA Meetings	13	RBA involved projects	N/A
MainstreamBIO's interview for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Project	1	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Link
Inclusion of synergy projects activities in MainstreamBIO's newsletter	3	ROBIN; BioRural; RuralBioUp	Link
Total	26		

MainstreamBIO successfully established **15 synergies** with EU-funded projects and initiatives operating in the bioeconomy and circular economy sectors. As a result of these partnerships **26 joint-activities** were carried out, including co-branded events; shared newsletters; social media campaigns and mutual support in implemented activities of various synergy projects. The project's active involvement in the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance establishment also played a central role in supporting collaboration at scale and enabling joint efforts such as the co-organisation of high-level events. Overall, the synergies established served as effective multipliers of MainstreamBIO's impact, helping ensure the sustainability and long-term visibility of its outcomes.

10. Monitoring and reporting framework

The effectiveness of MainstreamBIO's D&C strategy was guided by a structured and responsive monitoring and reporting framework. From the kickstart of the project, D&C activities were planned considering the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the GA. These included metrics such as number of website's unique visits, newsletters released, social media followers, participation in external events and promotional material distributed. As presented in Table 18, the framework also captured objective KPIs, such as the number of stakeholders reached, stakeholders engaged, joint actions with clustered projects, and stakeholders involved in exploitation and validation.

To track the progress against these KPIs, we relied on a combination of digital analytics tools, partner reporting inputs, and internal reviews. Website traffic was monitored through Google Analytics, providing insight into user behaviour, page visits, and engagement trends. Social media performance was tracked via platform-native tools (e.g. LinkedIn Analytics, Facebook Insights, and X metrics), helping to assess visibility and interaction levels in real time. These tools allowed the project team to gauge which types of content generated the highest engagement and to adapt communication tactics accordingly.

At the consortium level, all partners were required to document their dissemination efforts on a semester basis using standardised templates. These included the Dissemination Reporting Template and dedicated Internal and External Events Reporting Templates, which captured information on promotional activities, event participation, publications, and stakeholder engagement.

Additionally, throughout the project, results were reviewed regularly to assess performance against established targets. While many KPIs were met or even exceeded, some areas required targeted intervention, such as the number of unique visits to the project's website. In response, the communication team implemented adjustments such as increasing the promotion of the website's link through published content on both social media and website articles, and cross-promoting updates through newsletters and social media.

Table 18. DC & WP5 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators	Target	M18	M36
Unique visits to the project website	>15,000	2,817	8,719
External events/conferences attended	15	23	30
Number of newsletters released	6	3	6
Followers on social media	>1,000	950	1377
Views of the promotional video	> 500	257	1,300

Promotional material distributed ⁵	> 300	150	1,340
Nr. of stakeholders reached ⁶	20,000	10,021	27,029
Nr. of stakeholders engaged ⁷	3,000	560	4,101
Nr. of joint actions with clustered projects ⁸	>20	10	26
Nr. of stakeholders involved in exploitation validation	>50	20	58 ⁹

Although the KPI of 15,000 unique website visits was not fully reached, google analytics metrics indicate that the site was nevertheless an effective and actively used dissemination hub, as described in paragraph 5.3.1 of the same report. Over the course of the project, the website recorded more than 67,538 total events, generating 25,364 page views, 14,087 session starts, and over 17,504 user engagement events. Additionally, there were more than 2,201 tracked link clicks and 1,000 file downloads, showing clear interest in accessing deeper project content. This means that users not only visited the website but actively explored its content, initiating sessions, viewing multiple pages, and interacting with key features, resources, and downloads.

Furthermore, the website served as the primary access point for the project's Digital Toolkit, promotional materials, newsletters, public deliverables, and Open Call applications. Its role as a central information platform was further supported by ongoing cross-promotion through social media, newsletters, and project's events' presentations. When viewed in the context of the broader dissemination and engagement landscape, the website's performance complements a communication approach that prioritised quality, relevance, and stakeholder resonance over pure volume.

In summary, the monitoring and evaluation framework allowed MainstreamBIO to remain flexible and responsive, ensuring that communication activities continued to serve their purpose effectively even when specific targets required recalibration. The experience gained, particularly in balancing quantitative reach with qualitative depth, will serve as a valuable reference for future projects operating in similarly multi-layered stakeholder environments.

⁵ Promotional material distributed: Physical copies shared in internal/external events and digital copies downloaded from project's website

⁶ Stakeholders reached: website visitors; subscribers; followers; post reactions; video viewers; promotional material receivers; MIP members; participants in MainstreamBIO events; interviews and surveys participants; supported cases members; RBA & Synergies network

⁷ Stakeholders engaged: MIP members, MainstreamBIO events participants; interviews and surveys participants; supported cases members; subscribers; followers.

⁸ Joint actions: common participation in events, common digital presence activities, meetings/ workshops, common publications

⁹ 1st round: 20 (BM validation 17 cases + 3 AB members) (Questionnaire for Innovation Support services), 2nd round: 14 (Questionnaire for Innovation Support services); 24 Questionnaire for MIP members

11. Timeline and implementation plan

The dissemination and communication activities began at the start of the project with the production of promotional material, continued with a wide range of offline and online dissemination efforts, and were completed with the promotion of the project's final results at the project's final event. Below are the four distinct periods during which all our dissemination and communication activities were implemented:

→ First phase – early in the project (M1-M6):

Dissemination and communication efforts started early in the project when the D&C strategy was established. The D&C strategy focused on several key aspects, including the project's targeted stakeholders and tailored key messages to effectively them. Moreover, a monitoring framework was established to follow the progress of the relevant KPIs' metrics and ensure our strategy is effective. Additionally, the early stage of the project focused on creating a set of outreach materials and establishing the project's online presence and communication tools. Within the first six months of the project, the project's visual identity was developed, including a logo and a promotional package (such as leaflets, poster, templates, and letterheads). Lastly, the communication of the project to the broader public during these months was conducted through outreach to relevant EU projects, press releases, the first newsletter, and participation in external events.

→ Second phase – during the project (M7 - M25):

Throughout the course of the project, ongoing communication was maintained between the project's consortium and relevant stakeholders, fostered through the project's social media channels. Efforts were also made to build meaningful connections with other projects and initiatives focused on bioeconomy, sustainability, and the circular economy overall. During this core phase of MainstreamBIO, a wide range of project activities took place, including workshops, webinars, networking and demo days and joint activities with related European projects. Project outcomes were further highlighted through regular updates on the official website and a bi-annual newsletter, helping to extend the project's reach and influence. Additionally, consortium partners took part in external events and conferences, using these opportunities -and their existing ties within key industry networks- to broaden the project's exposure and connect with wider audiences.

→ Third phase – at the end of the project (M26 - M36):

Although the project's overall vision continued to be shared, this phase shifted focus toward showcasing its concrete results and outcomes. Especially toward the end, the data collected and lessons learned helped the consortium partners shape key policy recommendations aimed at supporting the uptake of biobased solutions in rural regions. A final dissemination event was also held in Brussels, bringing together key stakeholders, EU officials, and project partners to present the outcomes, and foster dialogue.

→ Fourth phase – Beyond the end of the project

To ensure the continued visibility and reach of the MainstreamBIO project, a variety of strategic platforms and tools will be utilised to maintain engagement well beyond the project's active phase. All project outputs, including datasets and publications, will be openly accessible via Zenodo, making the research available to policymakers, academics, and others with an interest in the field. The project's website will stay live for two years following the official end of the initiative, providing continued access to key information, deliverables, and supporting materials. The MainstreamBIO

consortium remains committed to preserving and expanding the project’s impact, ensuring that its outcomes continue to inform and engage relevant audiences long after the project concludes.

Figure 45. MainstreamBIO's DC timeline and implementation plan

12. Conclusions

Reflecting on the communication and dissemination strategy, it's clear that the MainstreamBIO project effectively shared its results with both a wide audience and its targeted stakeholder groups. Through its outreach activities, the project raised awareness among key actors, strengthened its presence within the EU landscape of related initiatives, and successfully conveyed its core outcomes and tools.

Throughout the project's duration, the consortium engaged over 4,101 stakeholders from across Europe and beyond. The diverse mix of communication tools, approaches, and activities enabled the team to connect with various target groups and, in many instances, surpass the original KPIs. A total of 131 events, including external, project-specific, and joint initiatives, further enhanced the project's outreach, while close cooperation with other relevant projects fostered strong synergies.

Regular updates to the project's website and social media channels, alongside biannual newsletters and creative promotional content, kept stakeholders informed and engaged. A major number (48) of public deliverables and other resources (publications; newsletter etc.) were made available via the project website and Zenodo, ensuring ongoing visibility and accessibility. The website will remain active for two years beyond the project's conclusion, until August 2027 continuing to serve as a repository for the project's materials and outputs.

During the entire project's duration, MainstreamBIO partners prioritised openness and knowledge sharing, aligning all data publications with FAIR principles to ensure they remain findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. These practices strengthen the long-term value of the project's research and facilitate future collaboration across scientific and policy communities.

Strategic collaborations, such as those with the RBA cluster, deepened the project's engagement in the biobased industry, enabling joint events, aligned strategies, and broader outreach. The consortium also contributed to capacity building across the biobased sector, equipping stakeholders with tools, knowledge, and skills to support biobased innovation.

Looking forward, the consortium is focused on ensuring its outcomes remain impactful and accessible. The project's policy recommendations and replication guide, shaped by practical experience and stakeholder feedback, are intended to guide the future adoption and upscaling of biobased solutions across Europe. Furthermore, the project's outcomes support key objectives of the EU Green Deal and Bioeconomy Strategy by advancing circular, sustainable solutions in the bioeconomy sector. These materials, along with the openly available tools, datasets, and reports, will continue to serve as a foundation for future innovation and policy alignment. By maintaining an active online presence and supporting ongoing collaborations, the project sets the stage for lasting contributions to the EU's green and circular economy ambitions.

Annexes

Annex 1: MainstreamBIO initial dissemination and communication guidelines for consortium partners

This document provides you with some key initial guidelines regarding communication and dissemination activities and introduces three main dissemination monitoring tools that you are kindly asked to use throughout the project.

I. Main guidelines

1. Actively contribute to the dissemination of project results and key messages.
2. Use the wording “MainstreamBIO” to refer to the project; do not use “MAINSTREAMBIO”.
3. For all your communications related to the project please include in your electronic signature the project logo, linked to the project’s website.
4. Do not forget to include the EU logo and the disclaimer:

**Funded by
the European Union**

- a. When displayed with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
 - b. You can download the needed EU emblem in the desired resolution following this link:
 - c. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/
5. If possible, follow the style guide concerning writing style, formatting options, numbers and currency, abbreviations and acronyms, captions, electronic cross-references, naming conventions, citation style. In general:
- Use Arial as font for documents generated with MS Office programmes and for web applications. The preferred spacing is 6 pt. before and after paragraph, whereas the preferred line spacing is single
 - Make sure to use the logo colour scheme for documents to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project
 - Whenever possible, use the logo letter type for promotional materials. If in doubt, check with WHITE.
 - Always use the same style for references, both for in-text citations and in the bibliography/footnotes
 - Be consistent in using currency references (for example, use EUR instead of € throughout)
 - Be consistent in the numbering format; comply with the British usage (e.g., 75,000,239.23), unless differently indicated.
 - If you abbreviate a word, use the correct abbreviation (for instance, “M” for million, not “mn”)
 - Make sure to introduce each abbreviation and acronym the first time you use it and create an abbreviation/acronym list at the beginning of the document
 - Review the language and the coherence of the structure of the text you drafted

6. Whenever possible, use the templates that will be provided to you, i.e., letterhead, presentation, publication. A leaflet and a poster will be prepared for you to use throughout the project. Other communication materials (e.g., infographics) will be prepared ad-hoc if needed.
7. **Always** inform WHITE and Q-PLAN regarding every dissemination and communication activity that you plan to carry out (e.g., organisation of an event, articles on websites or magazines, participation in an external event, etc.). This will enable us to publicise it through the project's communication channels in a timely manner.
8. You will have to report in detail all the dissemination actions you undertook (please see **Dissemination Reporting Template** for instructions).
9. Always report about meetings and events you organised and/or participated in (please see **Internal Events Reporting Template** for an explanation on how to report about events).
10. Inform WHITE and Q-PLAN about relevant events (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) in which MainstreamBIO partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. You have received an .xls file named "**External Conferences and Events**". All partners are kindly requested to fill in this specific .xls file, each time they identify an event relevant to project and share it with WHITE.
11. In compliance with GDPR requirements, always gather stakeholders' consent, when collecting, using and storing personal data during events/conferences. Please consider that pictures which make individuals identifiable are also considered personal data. Partners are responsible to gather participants' consent for the activities they undertake.

The above mentioned points will be updated when necessary in order to be in line with the project's requirements and progress.

The MainstreamBIO report "**Dissemination and communication plan**" (First version due in M3; Update in M18) will include these guidelines and will also outline the overall project's dissemination strategy and plan.

II. Website and Social Media use guidelines

This section provides you with some key initial guidelines regarding your expected contribution and use of the MainstreamBIO website and social media accounts (SMAs).

2.1 Website

Collect photos and videos for all MainstreamBIO activities and share them with WHITE., to make them usable on the website and on the MainstreamBIO SMAs.

1. Actively contribute (if possible, with 1 news item per month per partner) to the news section of the website. Please send each news item to WHITE. A news item can be anything, like a link to other similar projects/activities, an article about a new regulation, a notice regarding a new policy or initiative, an article about an event etc.
2. Inform WHITE regarding every event you organise or take part for the purposes of the project (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) and provide WHITE with a link to the event, so that it can be posted online in the dedicated section of the website
3. Inform WHITE about news articles (e.g., newspaper article, blogpost, TV interview etc.) mentioning your pilot area or the MainstreamBIO project and provide WR with a link/scan for giving it more visibility online.

III. Social Media Accounts

1. Connect with all MainstreamBIO SMAs (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) and use them accordingly: monitor announcements and posts, comment, like and retweet.
2. Do make your own posts to foster discussion and maintain the accounts' activity.
3. If you would like WHITE to publish a post on one or more of the SMAs (e.g., promote an event that is coming up in your city, announce the achievement of a milestone, etc.), please share the post using the dedicated Excel file on MS Teams ("MainstreamBIO External Conferences and Events.xlsx").
4. Promote the MainstreamBIO SMAs within your network of contacts.
5. Inform WHITE about any relevant profiles you may detect during the project, so that we can expand our network on SMAs.
6. If you create a short video, make any edits necessary in order to improve project's identity (add the project's name, logo, EU emblem, and the disclaimer included in the "Annex 1 – MainstreamBIO initial dissemination and communication guidelines for consortium partners"). WHITE is then accountable for uploading the video on YouTube.

The above-mentioned points will be updated when necessary, to be in line with the project's requirements and progress.

Annex 2: Dissemination Reporting Template

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of awareness and dissemination activities. Just to remind you, dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, meetings, workshops, interviews, press releases, publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. Please, complete any relevant parts of the form below each time you perform a dissemination activity either this is small or large.
Reporting frequency: Monthly basis

Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu.

No. of Action	Type of activity (Dissemination or Communication)	Category of activity (Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc. (In case of a social media post, make sure to specify the social media platform used [Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn])	Type of audience (in case the action reached more than one type of stakeholders please describe this type in the line below. Use as many lines as necessary)	Size of audience per type of stakeholder group (no. of persons per stakeholder group. For a social media post please add the views of the post)	Gender of audience per stakeholder group (Please specify only the number of women that participated in the activity)	Role and description of your organisation's involvement	Type of promotional material used	Quantity of promotional material distributed	Status of the dissemination activity	Short description of the dissemination/communication activity with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Relevant link	Other comments	Significant contacts made IF RELEVANT (name, position, organisation, if consent to store and share data was given, add also address, tel, fax, e-mail)	
1	Dissemination activity	Social Media Post	Kick-off meeting Post on LinkedIn	Citizens/general public	675	N/A	Author	Project Logo/Info	1	Consort	Post on the Q PLAN's Social Media disseminating the holding of the MainstreamBIO kick-off meeting and the official project start in Thessaloniki, on the 29th of September 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/q-plan-horizoneurpe-bio-rural-activity-6983451570831036416-3sb57utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	Posted on Tuesday, Oct 5, 2022	N/A	
			Kick-off meeting Post on Facebook		174	N/A			1						https://www.facebook.com/2FQPlaninternational%2Fposts%2Fpermalink%2FpostId%2F1020623No5X7Jat35InV2Hep43UeWp0dcm5AuNtjPKuwyEhRa3TVHrge91ZDWrKkEVI
			Kick-off meeting Post on Twitter		140	N/A			1						https://twitter.com/Q_PLANintl/status/1577691846607773705
2	Dissemination activity	Website post	Project Overview Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL website	Citizens/general public	19	N/A	Author	Project Logo/Info	1	Delivered	Post on the Q PLAN's website presenting the MainstreamBIO's overview and the role and responsibilities of Q PLAN in MainstreamBIO project	https://qplan-intl.gr/projects/mainstreambio/	Posted on Wednesday, Oct 5, 2022	N/A	
3	Communication activity	Workshop	"Projects2Projects" Mobilisation and Mutual learning workshop	Other	Around 60	N/A	Discussant	Presentation	1	Delivered	Q PLAN shared during the workshop an overview of MainstreamBIO's main objectives and activities	https://www.transition2bio.eu/event/projects2projects/	Organized on Wednesday, Oct 5, 2022	N/A	
4	Clustering activity	Collaboration with other EU-funded projects	Meeting between MainstreamBIO, BioRural, RuralBioUp, SCALE-UP projects	Other	10	3	Speaker	Presentation	1	Delivered	Organisation of a first meeting between the 4 projects with the aim to give an overview of each project and explore potential areas for collaboration during the projects' lifetime	N/A	Organized on Monday, Dec 19, 2022	N/A	
5	Clustering activity	Collaboration with other EU-funded projects	Workplans	Other	5	1	Participant	Other	1	Delivered	Communication via e-mails between Q PLAN and the Coordinator of BioRural project with the aim to exchange the projects' workplans and explore potential synergies between them	N/A	September, 2022	N/A	

Figure 46. MainstreamBIO's Dissemination Reporting Template

Annex 3: Internal Events Reporting Template

Event's Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organisers	
Audience (number and type)	
Duration	

Stakeholders reached

What type of stakeholders were engaged?

- Define the type(s) of stakeholders reached (policy, SMEs, general public etc.)
- How many people attended?
- How many women attended?

Event's goals, objectives and relevance with MainstreamBIO

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc). Was the event relevant to MainstreamBIO? To what extent?

Organisation of the event

In case of organising a project's event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

- How was the event/activity organised?
- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Dissemination activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the MainstreamBIO project promoted during the event?

Structure of the event (short minutes)

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

**For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

- What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Evaluation of the event

- What are the main impressions and observation that you made?
- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

ANNEX: Attachments

- ✓ The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- ✓ A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if possible)
- ✓ The agenda of the event
- ✓ Photos (please make sure to have the consent of participants to use them)
- ✓ Presentations (if applicable)
- ✓ -Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g., links to press releases, videos, posts, leaflets etc.

Annex 4: External Events Reporting Template

No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Abbreviation	Date	Location	Registration fees	Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)	Website	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission, ...)	Added by (Partner)
1	"Projects2Projects" Mobilisation and Mutual learning workshop	EU Horizon Europe projects		10/5/2022	AEC Building CDMA, Brussels	Free of charge	N/A	https://www.transition2bio.eu/event/projects2projects/	Mandatory Registration	Q: PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q PLAN)
2	European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	Biomass Resources and Potential	EURCE	08/06/2023	Bologna, Italy	€30 Euro/day	31/03/2023	https://www.eurce.com/	Abstract Submission	MINISTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY (MTU)
3	EXPOBIOMASA	Biomass Resources and Potential	EXPOBIOMASA	09/05/2023	Valladolid, Spain	Free of charge (we were invited by BioRural)	N/A	https://expobiomasa.com/en/actividades-paralelas/innovaciones	Preparation of a presentation and infosheet	EURIZON SL (INNOVARUM or INNV)
4	COOPID final event	Bioeconomy cooperation and knowledge transfer	COOPID final event	31/05/2023	Brussels, Belgium	Free of charge (we were invited by BioRural)	N/A	https://coopid.eu/coopid-bioeconomy-week4#bioeconomyConference	Mandatory Registration	EURIZON SL (INNOVARUM or INNV)
5	II Bioeconomy Forum from Castilla y León	Regional bioeconomy forum	BFCyL	26/10/2023	Soria, Spain	Free of charge (we were invited by BioRural)	N/A	https://forodebioeconomia.es/#Programa	Mandatory Registration	EURIZON SL (INNOVARUM or INNV)
6	Circular Bioeconomy Forum in Seville	National bioeconomy forum		21/11/2023	Sevilla, Spain	Free of charge	N/A	https://www.forobioeconomiacircular.com/	Mandatory Registration	EURIZON SL (INNOVARUM or INNV)
7	Clusters Meet Regions	II Rural/Bioeconomy project focus group II Bioeconomy Session		21-23/11/2023	Iasi, Romania	Free of charge	N/A	https://clustercollaboration.eu/content/clusters-meet-regions-iasi-romania	i) Preparation of a presentation ii) Participation in Rural/Bioeconomy focus group	Q: PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q PLAN)
8	Stakeholder Meeting DLEAF4VALUE	II Biomass resources and bioeconomy II DLEAF4VALUE stakeholder meeting		30/01/2024	Madrid, Spain	Free of charge		https://ajed4value.eu/challenges-opportunities-for-biobased-products/	Preparation of a presentation and infosheet	EURIZON SL (INNOVARUM or INNV)
9	Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival main event	Youth as driver of transformative change		13-14/03/2024	Brussels, Belgium	Free of charge	N/A	https://research-innovation-community.europa.eu/events/27b3k4wDnTfAmP0TtCh/overview https://www.fairtrade-europe.eu/en/news/all-research-and-innovation-how-to-use-date-bioeconomy-changemakers-festival-13-14-march-2024-2023-12-13_en	RBA stand, mandatory registration	Q: PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q PLAN)
10	Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival - Thessaloniki satellite event	Youth as driver of transformative change		3/14/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	Free of charge	N/A		Printed banner, leaflets	Q: PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q PLAN)
11	IX European Rural Development Network Conference "Green transformation in the European rural areas"	Green transformation in the European rural areas; ERDN		11-13/09/2024	Vilnius, Lithuania	N/A	30/03/2024	https://erdn.eu/conference/2024/03/24/	Abstract Submission	INSTITUTE OF SOIL SCIENCE AND PLANT CULTIVATION (IUNG)
12	Participation at National Ploughing Championships of Ireland	Focus on farmers and technology innovation - field event	NPAI	21/09/2023	Portlaoise, Ireland	N/A	N/A	https://www.npa.ie/	N/A	MINISTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY (MTU)
13	Finalist in Better Farming Awards - Attended Award Ceremony	Focus on sustainable innovation in farming	Agrinsider	30/11/2023	Laois, Ireland	Ticket purchased - 239.85	N/A	https://betterfarmingawards.com/?h=best17ch20better20farm20awards2020w20ch20awards202020award20sustainable20sector	N/A	MINISTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY (MTU)
14	Go-Grass Final Conference	Focus on dissemination of rural small-scale bioeconomy business models	Go-Grass	12/03/2023	Brussels, Belgium	N/A	N/A	https://www.go-grass.eu/	N/A	MINISTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY (MTU)
15	CBE-AJ, BIC, CEE2ACT - Promoting Bioeconomy in Greece	Latest developments, challenges, and opportunities in the Bioeconomy field, as well as co-design the next steps towards drawing a National Bioeconomy strategy for Greece		15/4/2024	Athens, Greece	Free of charge	N/A	https://www.cbe.europa.eu/events/cbe-aj-bic-cee2act-promoting-bioeconomy-greece	N/A	Q: PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q PLAN)
16	Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference	From Science To Transition	NWBC	Nordic	Ornskoldsvik, Sweden	Ticket purchased	25th of April 2024	https://www.n.se/en/what-we-do/projects/nordic-wood-biorefinery-conference-2024	Mandatory Registration, preparation of poster and abstract.	RISE PROCESSUM AB (PRC)
17	Biorircular Summit	Forum on Bioeconomy focused on national (Spanish) and European policy, regulatory aspects (energy, fuels, renewable gases, circular economy, waste), related sectors (agriculture, livestock, forestry, all types of industries), sustainability, positive impact and innovation.		11/12/2023	Madrid, Spain	280€/person	18/01/2025 (Poster)	https://biorircularsummit.es/	Mandatory registration, preparation of poster	EURIZON SL (INNOVARUM or INNV)
18	ROBIN Stakeholders Engagement Event (Region of Central Macedonia)			29/5/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	N/A		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201524175871014696/?updateEntityId=urn:li:activity:7201524175871014696		Q: PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q PLAN)
19	BioNets project cross-fertilisation meeting (online)	Presentation of MIP by Magdalena Borzecka during the Cross-fertilisation meeting of BioNets Forest and Agricultural Network webinar.		11/12/2024	Online			https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=8890162300580078&set=em.566586296978		INSTITUTE OF SOIL SCIENCE AND PLANT CULTIVATION (IUNG)
20	IV Summit of Polish Operation Groups in Łódź			5-7/11/2024	Warsaw			https://sites.google.com/site/opergr/w112024		CULTIVATION (IUNG)
21	BIC Matchmaking event			8/2/2024	Reyers 80, 1030 Brussels			https://biosortium.eu/event/matchmaking-event-2024		RISE PROCESSUM AB (PRC)
22	Bioeconomy (MIP) 2023			22/2/2023	Agricultural University – Plovdiv	N/A		https://www.plovdiv.bg/en/2023/02/22/bioeconomy-mip-2023		AGPI
23	Workshop held under the CAPBIO4BC project			15/4/2023	Agricultural University – Plovdiv	N/A		https://www.plovdiv.bg/en/2023/04/15/bioeconomy-workshop		AGPI

Figure 47. MainstreamBio's External Events Reporting Template

Annex 5: MainstreamBIO's Leaflet; Poster & Banner

PROJECT'S INFORMATION

MainstreamBIO is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project which sets out to get small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe, by offering tailored innovation support services and innovative digital tools which will enhance the engagement of key rural actors and create sustainable value chains and business models supporting the development of the EU bioeconomy.

The project provides free access in a Multi-actor Innovation Platform, where regional stakeholders with diverse backgrounds, expertise and interests are members and build networks and partnerships between them, but also free of charge innovation support services and an open access Toolkit.

PROJECT ID

Project name: MainstreamBIO "Mainstreaming small-scale bio-based solutions across rural Europe"
Grant Agreement: 101059420
Programme: Horizon Europe
Type of action: HORIZON-CSA
Start date: 1 September 2022
Duration: 36 months
EU contribution: 2,999,031,25 €
Coordinator: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

OUR TEAM

	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL (Q-PLAN) MainstreamBIO's Coordinator www.qplan-intl.gr/ Greece
	Munster Technological University (MTU) www.mtu.ie/ Ireland
	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (FBCD) www.foodbiocluster.dk/ Denmark
	Innovarum (INN) www.innovarum.es/en/home/ Spain
	Wageningen University & Research (WR) www.wur.nl/ Netherlands
	Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation (IUNG) www.iung.pl/ Poland
	White Research SRL (WHITE) www.white-research.eu/ Belgium
	Draxis Environmental SA (DRAXIS) www.draxis.gr/ Greece
	Agricultural University – Plovdiv (AUP) www.auplovdiv.bg/en/ Bulgaria
	Rise Processum AB (PROC) www.rise.se/en/processum Sweden

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CONTACT US: Info@mainstreambio-project.eu

Funded by the European Union

MAINSTREAM BIO

Mainstreaming small-scale bio-based solutions in rural Europe

www.mainstreambio-project.eu

CHALLENGE

The potential of bio-based products and solutions in developing a sustainable economy has been recognized in the EU Bioeconomy strategy. Though, despite considerable investments in research, innovation, and business support, many EU regions have yet to realize this potential.

This is where MainstreamBIO comes into play! MainstreamBIO aims to support the deployment of small-scale bio-based solutions across EU's rural regions by establishing regional Multi-actor Innovation Platforms (MIPs) in 7 EU countries (Netherlands, Poland, Denmark, Sweden, Bulgaria, Spain, Ireland), in the aim of co-creating sustainable business model pathways in line with regional potentials and policy initiatives.

OBJECTIVES

- 01** Deliver a catalogue of small-scale bio-based technologies, business models and social innovations for cross-case comparison and assessment of opportunities for business endeavours
- 02** Collect the best practices for improved nutrient recycling, to successfully manage nutrients and organic matter recycling back to soils
- 03** Develop a Decision Support System, which matches the available biomass and waste streams with small-scale bio-based technologies, business models and social innovations
- 04** Create a Bioeconomy Repository, whose purpose is to aggregate educational material from such bio-based projects and raise awareness on bioeconomy educational resources
- 05** Establish a BioForum, to communicate, exchange ideas, solutions and good practices and connect with other members of the Multi-actor Innovation Platforms
- 06** Provide recommendations tailored to key target groups for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels
- 07** Deliver technical and business services, supporting the introduction of bio-based solutions, products and services to the market

WHO WILL BENEFIT FROM THE PROJECT?

- Farmers, foresters and biomass producers
- Governments & policy makers
- Bioeconomy value chain actors
- Regional bioeconomy & sustainability actors
- Academia & scientific community
- General public

Figure 48. MainstreamBIO's Leaflet

Figure 49. MainstreamBIO's poster

MAINSTREAM BIO

**MAINSTREAMING
SMALL-SCALE
BIO-BASED
SOLUTIONS ACROSS
RURAL EUROPE**

MainstreamBIO aims to accelerate the deployment of small-scale bio-based solutions across Europe via Multi-Actor Innovation Platforms and tailored innovation support in seven countries (Netherlands, Poland, Denmark, Sweden, Bulgaria, Spain, Ireland).

TAILORED BUSINESS AND TECHNICAL SERVICES BY EXPERTS AND PRACTICAL DIGITAL TOOLS TO SUPPORT DEPLOYMENT OF SMALL-SCALE BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR:

- FARMERS, FORESTERS AND BIOMASS PRODUCERS
- BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAIN ACTORS
- GOVERNMENT AND POLICY MAKERS
- GENERAL PUBLIC

VISIT: www.mainstreambio-project.eu

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CONSORTIUM

Funded by the European Union

Figure 50. MainstreamBIO's banner

Annex 6: EuRCBC Agenda

European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference

DAY 1: 13/05/2025 | Comet Louise 6th floor, Brussels

AGENDA

Schedule	Sessions	
09:00-09:30	Welcoming Breakfast & Registration	
09:30-10:00	Michael Losch, European Commission - Coordinator for Bioeconomy Marco Rupp, Biobased Industries Consortium	
10:00-11:20	Fire-pitching of hosting projects <i>MainstreamBIO</i> <i>ROBIN</i> <i>Biorural</i> <i>BIOMODEL4REGIONS</i> <i>SCALE UP</i> <i>RuralBioUP</i>	L. Parodos, Q-PLAN International C. Politis, Q-PLAN International A.T. Balafoutis, CERTH P. Circelli, META Group H. Gerdes, Ecologic Institute K. Jurkiewicz, APRE
11:20-11:30	Coffee break	
11:30-12:30	<i>Panel discussion</i> Diverse Perspectives on Bioeconomy: Exploring how different approaches complement each other to enhance the EU's bioeconomy	D. Grozdanic, Munster Technological University Z. Kiresiewa, Ecologic Institute N. BARGUES, Greenovate Europe L. Vivani, Moverim
12:30-13:30	Lunch Buffet	
13:30-15:00	Tools for Advancing the EU's Bioeconomy: Supporting local communities, policymakers, and entrepreneurs in adopting sustainable practices	C. Roth, Steinbeis Europa Zentrum P. Kafkias, DRAXIS Environmental A. Pindur, Business Upper Austria F. Feil, Biomass Technology Group A. Balafoutis, CERTH
15:00-15:15	Coffee break	
15:15-16:30	<i>Panel discussion</i> Inspiring Change Through Success Stories: Real-world applications driving innovation and adoption across regions	M.G. Alegre, Technological Corporation of Andalusia Mar Cátedra, Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural (Andalusia region) G. Anzaldúa, Ecologic Institute B. Deltoro, Innovarum T. Bullová, SK Bioeconomy Cluster A. Liaigre, ERRIN Network
16:30-16:45	Signing Memorandum of Collaboration among ROBIN regions (Andalusia, Zilina, Central Macedonia, Southern Regional Assembly and Baden-Wuerttemberg)	
16:45-17:15	Wrap up and Networking	

Figure 51. EuRCBC Agenda_Day#1

European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference

DAY 2: 14/05/2025 | [Comet Louise](#), Brussels

AGENDA

Schedule	Sessions		
08:50-09:30	Welcoming Breakfast & Registration		
ROOM 3.4			
09:30-11:00	Keynote speech : Pathway towards the new EU Bioeconomy Strategy (15') <i>T. Calikowski, DG Research and Innovation, European Commission</i> Presentation of joint policy observations from RuralBioUp, MainstreamBio, SCALE-UP and BioRural (40') Panel discussion and Q&A session (35')		
11:00-11:15	Coffee break		
	ROOM 3.4	ROOM 4.4	ROOM 6.4
11:15-13:30	Policy round table “Implementation of small-scale BIO-based solutions across rural Europe” organised by MainstreamBIO	ROBIN Train-the-Trainer Workshop: Scaling the Bioeconomy Through ROBIN's Toolbox, Policies, and Strategies	International Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop “Building Bridges in Bioeconomy: From Regional Partnerships to Future Pathways for Europe” - organised by RuralBioUp and Biomodel4Regions
13:30-14:30	Light lunch		

Figure 52. EuRCBC Agenda_Day#2

MAINSTREAM BIO
MAINSTREAMING SMALL-SCALE BIO-BASED
SOLUTIONS ACROSS RURAL EUROPE

The project

MainstreamBIO is an Horizon Europe EU funded project, which sets out to get small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe, providing a broader range of rural actors with the opportunity to engage in and speed up the development of the bioeconomy. Recognizing the paramount importance of bioeconomy for addressing key global environmental and societal challenges, MainstreamBIO develops regional Multi-actor Innovation Platforms in 7 EU countries (PL, DK, SE, BG, ES, IE & NL). The project aims to enhance cooperation among key rural players towards co-creating sustainable business model pathways in line with regional potentials and policy initiatives. MainstreamBIO supports 35 multiactor partnerships to overcome barriers and get bio-based innovations to market with hands-on innovation support, accelerating the development of over 70 marketable bio-based products and services. Furthermore, the project develops and employs a digital toolkit to better match bio-based technologies, social innovations and good nutrient recycling practices with available biomass and market trends as well as to enhance understanding of the bioeconomy with a suite of educational resources building on existing research results and tools. To achieve these targets, MainstreamBIO involves 10 partners across Europe, coming from various fields. Thus, all partners combine their knowledge and experience to promote the growth of bioeconomy in a sustainable and inclusive manner.

Coordinator: **Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q-PLAN)**

Partner		Short Name
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	MTU
	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR
	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG
	RISE PROCESSUM AB	PROC
	AGRAREN UNIVERSITET - PLOVDIV	AUP
	FBCD AS	FBCD
	EURIZON SL	INN
	DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL SA	DRAXIS
	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WHITE

CONTACT US info@mainstreambio-project.eu **VISIT** www.mainstreambio-project.eu

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MainstreamBio Project

MainstreamBio Horizon Europe Project